

Ref. Ares(2025)5707664 - 14/07/2025

B.RIGHT SPACES

BETTER RIGHTS IN BETTER
CIVIC SPACE

REPORT ON THE PATHWAYS FOR MUTUAL LEARNING

National Level

Deliverable 3.2

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project data:	B.RIGHT PLACES Project ID: 101142977 Call reference: CERV-2023-CHAR-LITI
Deliverable No.	3.2
Work Package:	3
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Date of submission:	14/07/2025

We want to clarify that the use of English in this Document has been checked with the online AI-enhanced tool “DeepL.com” (free versions), for improvement of the writing style and clarity. We have then reviewed the resulting contents to ensure consistency with our original texts and correspondence with the Consortium’s vision and priorities.

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Introduction

This report is part of the European B.RIGHT SPACES project, whose primary objective is to create favourable conditions for developing ecosystems that support civic spaces. Through a mutual learning process at national and local levels (referring to project partners and represented territorial experiences), the project has conducted a series of "policy labs," focus groups, and workshops in various European cities, involving a wide range of local actors, including municipal councils, academics, cultural professionals, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), residents, and activists. The objective of this initiative was to explore the role of civic spaces as urban democratic infrastructures and strengthen their capacity to promote participation and social cohesion. The general report is the product of a series of in-depth actions that characterized the project's main activities:

- National Reports.
- Documentation produced through workshops and focus groups.
- Documentation regarding the Policy Labs.
- Desk research on digital civic spaces.

The contexts from which specific evidence and cross-cutting analyses were drawn were the following:

- Torres Vedras (Portugal).
- Barcelona (Spain).
- Warsaw (Poland).
- Turin (Italy).
- Rome (Italy).

Through the comparison of local experiences and knowledge, the report aims to provide a holistic understanding of the characteristics and specificities of civic spaces, the critical issues that hinder their full development, and the proposed development paths to strengthen their potential.

1. The National Reports

1.1 B. RIGHT SPACES in Torres Vedras

Overview	
<p>The Torres Vedras City Council and EMERGE developed four themes in the cultural context as a matrix for the development of civic spaces in the city of Torres Vedras. Experts on the topics of cultural policies, accessibility, communication, and youth were invited. Technicians from the Torres Vedras City Council, academics from Portuguese universities, cultural professionals who work in this municipality and independent cultural professionals participated. Most of the meetings were held online, only one was held in a double format.</p> <p>At the beginning of each session, Nicolle Santos gave a brief presentation on the B.Right Spaces project, showing the definition of civic spaces and the research phases that this project went through and the current point at which it is.</p> <p>All sessions were moderated by Nicole Santos from Torres Vedras City Council and Jorge Reis from EMERGE - Cultural Association.</p>	
1. Introduction	
<p>Brief background of the sessions</p>	<p>The policy lab on the impact of cultural policies included Luís Soldado, from AREPO, an association with inclusive projects in the area of opera; José Carlos Mota, researcher and professor at the University of Aveiro in the area of urban planning, with his own projects in the city of Aveiro involving the community; and Magda Matias, artistic director of the ESTUFA association, a school of dance, theatre and illustration, focusing on children and young people.</p> <p>The accessibility focus group was attended by André Batista, architect from Torres Vedras City Council, Pedro Almeida from iKi Technology, a technology company that develops software that promotes accessibility for people with low vision or visual impairments. Silvia Silva, Head of Social Development Division at Municipality of Torres Vedras Torres, and Sónia Costa, Senior technician in special education and rehabilitation.</p> <p>The focus group on communication and youth included Rita Pereira from the Associação Académico de Torres Vedras, responsible for the project “Somos Comunidade”; Pedro Fortunato, Head of the Communication and Brand Division at Municipality of Torres Vedras; Joana Agostinho, technician at the youth area of Municipality of Torres Vedras; Carolina Marques, Researcher and PhD student at, ISCTE-IUL; Miguel Neto Head of the Education Division at Municipality of Torres Vedras; Sílvia Silva, Head of the Social Development Division at Municipality of Torres Vedras; Sara Battesti, professor in the area of cultural communication, having worked for many years on large-scale projects such as biennials and festivals, but also on social projects; Catarina Sobreiro, Head of the Culture, Cultural Heritage and Tourism Division; and Teresa Oliveira, Professor at the Faculty of Economics, University of Coimbra.</p> <p>All participants were contacted by email and confirmed their presence and interest by the same means.</p> <p>The policy labs and focus groups took place on the following dates:</p>

	<p>Policy lab impact of cultural policies 22nd April. 2025 3 pm (<i>in person and online</i>)</p> <p>Accessibility focus group 9th June 2025 10 am. (<i>online</i>)</p> <p>Communication and youth focus group 9th June 2025 2.30 pm (<i>online</i>)</p>
<p>Overview of how data were collected</p>	<p>The method used for the policy lab and the two focus groups was exposition and brainstorming. All those present participated by highlighting their experience in each topic and were invited to identify what could be improved.</p>
<p>2. Main findings</p>	
<p>Políticas culturais <i>Cultural Policies</i></p>	<p>Key findings:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The cultural policies currently being implemented in the territory of Torres Vedras were preceded by participatory processes where cultural professionals were able to contribute to policies that are more appropriate to the context of the network of associations. 2. The cultural policies implemented favour the democratisation of culture and promote fruitful intersections for the development of audiences, through mediation actions promoted by the municipality and local entities. 3. The municipality develops networking environments that promote cooperation between institutions. One example is the Torres Vedras Culture Network, which has been implemented since last year and involved consulting all stakeholders working in the area. <p>Trends:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Most cultural agents in Torres Vedras are pleased with the cultural policies developed by the current cultural council. 2. It was also mentioned that the institutions have developed a good sense of cooperation, especially with regard to attracting new forms of financing that enable their strengthening. <p>Insights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The municipality of Torres Vedras provides democratic access to regulated annual and biannual financial support. The programs promote broader access, covering a larger number of institutions that are rapidly growing. • However, these programs do not include the payment of fees, a situation that is in line with the national programs to support arts and culture promoted by the Portuguese Republic through the Directorate-General for the Arts. • Despite the programs, the municipality directly supports some local institutions with higher amounts than those of the programs mentioned. A situation that still causes some distrust on the part of institutions towards the municipality. • Still, the Municipality is a partner in projects run by local associations, often taking on the role of co-producer, facilitating

	<p>agreements that are welcome in national programs to support arts and culture.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Furthermore, the municipality has contracted local entities to manage projects in the territory and has integrated local entities into European support programs, whenever possible. ● The policy of providing in-kind support to entities has operated on a one-off basis. It could take on a more transparent and practical dimension so that all resources could be optimized. ● The policy of providing spaces to associations is always facilitated although, at the moment, due to the high number of new institutions, the Council has begun to find it difficult to allocate more spaces. It no longer has many solutions. In the same chapter, some local associations benefit from support for renting the space where they carry out their activities. ● In addition, the municipality is also a cultural programmer, which is problematic for the development of audiences for the private sector. The examples given were: A concert hall has tickets on sale for €7.50 and the same band is presented at the Teatro Cine de Torres Vedras with tickets costing €5. This principle of competitiveness could be avoided if there were greater coordination between public and private programmers. But it would not happen at all if the municipality did not program. The suggestion is that the municipality could, instead of programming, annually hire local entities to take on this programming in the facilities that the city has and festivals that it organizes, on a rotating basis. ● Private companies have little room to attract the public, when the municipality programmes with considerable intensity.
<p>Accessibilidade <i>Accessibility</i></p>	<p>Key findings:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital platforms are a space for freedom of expression as a civic space. 2. There must be education focused on the use of digital space, its advantages and disadvantages, and the danger of misinformation and confusion. 3. Architectural space and urban planning cannot enter into friction and entropy with its civic use. <p>Trends:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financing programs help, but can, at the same time, condition social and cultural projects. 2. Digital space does not replace physical civic space. <p>Insights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital platforms are used in a hasty manner. ● In education and information provided by the media, there must be rules and limits on the use of these platforms and, on the other hand, how we access these digital civic spaces.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The physical space promotes closer encounters and direct relational contact. ● In architectural projects for squares, new buildings, cultural and social facilities, and heritage rehabilitation, there is always a concern that these are accessible to everyone. ● There is a lack of more evident and closer access to the communication of what is being done, because attention amidst the noise of the excess of information is low.
<p>Juventude <i>Youth</i></p>	<p>Key findings:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The use of spaces is enhanced by access to the Internet with regard to younger ages. 2. Communication needs to be clearer and more concise for young people. 3. Mobility is crucial for young people's civic participation. <p>Trends:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Youth civic participation is a challenge. 2. Activities are communicated in an institutional way, which alienates young people. <p>Insights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The municipality of Torres Vedras encourages young people to have active civic participation. A specific plan was developed so that they could participate in political decisions by promoting greater awareness of the importance of active youth participation. ● Entities have to communicate a lot, but young people don't look for it. ● Regarding other projects, uptake is relatively low. Many times they are encouraged by their parents. ● It is difficult to have a good response to youth volunteering. It has been decreasing over the years. There has to be something in return. It must first be communicated in schools to educate about the importance, value and emotional benefit, to encourage experimentation. It would be better if this could be done online. ● What if the digital models of Whatsapp groups and other online groups, and forums, are the spaces where young people today are most comfortable to participate civically? ● The lack of volunteering has to do with a society that has turned towards individualism.
<p>Comunicação <i>Communication</i></p>	<p>Key findings:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication has to happen in education, then in the creation of partnerships, protocols with public institutions, volunteer grants, and senior colleges. 2. Civic participation is difficult, but when people commit, the loyalty rate is very high. 3. Civic participation is intergenerational and intercultural.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. If we really want people to participate, we have to understand what their needs are. 5. The right to information is constitutionally guaranteed. 6. Absence and non-participation is also a form of expression. 7. The consultative and participatory bodies are too institutionalized, in which the general population is not qualified to participate. 8. It is not considered that people do not have access to information on the cultural activities of municipal cultural facilities. There is a good level of participation in the activities promoted by the municipality. Even those that require registration are often full. <p>Trends:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. People have the information available, but there is no trigger that promotes the search for that information. 2. Digital platforms are not accessible, which creates an exclusion gap. <p>Insights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The municipality only communicates its own events or those co-organized with local institutions. Entities that have municipal support do not have their activities publicized by the municipality. • Our citizenry is relatively untrusting. Civic participation must have access to great communication elasticity. • It may not be so much a communication failure as a cultural issue. Teachers who are outraged that students do not participate civically are the same people who do not participate. Good examples of civic participation in the family are not given. • There is an individual right to not want to know. • The cacophony of communication contributes to confusion that makes it unclear how people can participate. • The fact that few people go, or don't go, is, in itself, also a form of civic participation that says that the subject is not of interest.
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3. Challenges and barriers: Summary of major challenges identified

Impact of cultural policies

The cultural programming stance that the municipality of Torres Vedras has with strong intensity causes some problems for the development of audiences for the private sector.

There is a massive overlap of activities carried out by the municipality that weaken or take away opportunities from the private sector.

Accessibility

Financing programs can condition the objectives of social and cultural projects, and the urgency that the two sectors represent does not match their timing.

Youth

Communication is not clear and concise, and it is also too institutionalized, which alienates young people.

The lack of mobility solutions limits young people's civic participation.

The lack of volunteering has to do with a society that has become more individualistic.

Communication

There is a lack of something that promotes the search for information that public and private social and cultural entities make available physically and digitally.

The culture of the Portuguese people may be the conditioning element in access to information.

There is an individual right to not want to know.

4. Opportunities and strengths: Summary of positive aspects or enabling factors observed

Impact of cultural policies

The cultural policies implemented by the Municipality of Torres Vedras City favour the democratisation of the cultural fabric in access to the financial support programs that it provides.

The municipality develops networking environments promoting cooperation between entities with the implementation of the Torres Vedras Culture Network.

Accessibility

In the architectural projects that the municipality of Torres Vedras implements, there is always a concern that they are accessible to everyone.

Youth

In schools, young people must be made aware of the importance, value and emotional benefit of volunteering.

Communication

Communication can play an important role in creating bonds of trust between institutions and people, in order to achieve a high loyalty rate.

Additionally, it is significant to extend this to education, then in the creation of partnerships, protocols with public institutions, volunteer grants, and senior colleges.

5. Proposals and recommendations: Proposed strategies and actions categorised by priority or timeline (short-term, medium-term, long-term...)

Short-term

Create an educational program focused on the use of digital space as a civic space.

Make digital models of Whatsapp groups and other online groups and forums the spaces where young people exercise their civic participation.

A study of audiences should be carried out to understand their sociocultural needs.

Medium-term

The Municipality of Torres Vedras could improve the coordination of public programming to foster closer dialogue with the private sector, or alternatively, the private sector could refrain from taking on a programming role entirely. A potential solution would be to annually hire local organisations to manage the programming of the city's facilities and the festivals it organises, on a rotational basis.

Additionally, the Municipality of Torres Vedras could offer better support to local entities in promoting the activities it funds, by facilitating the use of its communication channels and providing spaces across the city for displaying posters and information.

Long-term	
<p>Create a private sponsorship fund to complement the municipality's support programs.</p> <p>Social economy entities must coordinate with cultural entities to develop projects focused on people and their social and cultural needs.</p>	
6. Possible future activities to protect, promote and support civic space in the territory	
Action plan, responsibilities, deadlines	Not applicable
7. Conclusion: Final remarks and next steps	
<p>Although there is currently no perfect harmony between the public and private sectors regarding their respective roles as promoters of civic and cultural spaces, encouraging signs of collaborative efforts between local entities offer hope for a more integrated future. These emerging cooperative networks signal the potential for a future in which the balance between the public and private sectors is more equitable, with clearer delineations of responsibility and less overlap. As a result, both sectors will be able to play to their strengths while fostering a collaborative environment that maximizes their collective impact</p> <p>Social and cultural organisations, through increased collaboration, will be able to work more cohesively, promoting civic spaces in a more expansive and interconnected manner. This broader approach could ensure that cultural initiatives are not just isolated events, but part of a continuous, ongoing conversation that reflects the diverse needs and aspirations of the community. In such a scenario, cultural programming could be more inclusive, accessible, and relevant to all segments of society.</p> <p>Furthermore, support programmes aimed at the cultural and social sectors could evolve to be more responsive, efficient, and aligned with the unique challenges faced by these sectors. By reducing bureaucratic hurdles and creating more flexible frameworks, these programmes could respond more effectively to the fragility of the cultural sector and the urgent needs of the social sector. Streamlining these processes would allow for quicker, more direct intervention, enabling local entities to address pressing community needs without unnecessary delays.</p> <p>Education and communication will also be crucial in fostering a culture of trust and democratic participation, particularly among young people. By using these tools strategically, municipalities and local organisations can build stronger connections within the community, encouraging an active and informed citizenry. Engaging young people in these processes will ensure that future generations are equipped with the knowledge and motivation to take part in shaping their civic environment.</p> <p>Moreover, the digital space presents a unique opportunity to redefine civic engagement. With the growing reliance on digital platforms, the online realm can be transformed into a primary civic space for citizens to access information, engage in dialogue, and participate in decision-making processes. By creating accessible, intuitive, and inclusive digital platforms, civic participation can become more widespread, faster, and easier, ensuring that no one is left behind in the democratic process.</p> <p>Urban space is naturally evolving, especially as people change how they use it. As society adapts to new ways of living, public spaces must evolve to reflect these changes. This transformation requires both flexibility and inclusivity in their design, ensuring that public spaces are not only functional but also welcoming to diverse groups. Public spaces should be designed with the long-term goal of creating environments where people want to stay, not merely pass through.</p>	

Both physical infrastructure and cultural attitudes play a significant role in how people participate in public life. Public spaces should be more than just physical environments; they must be vibrant hubs that encourage interaction, engagement, and democratic participation. In that sense, fostering civic spaces should go beyond infrastructure to include cultural shifts that empower communities to take ownership of these spaces.

The municipality of Torres Vedras can strengthen these efforts by developing deeper, more sustainable connections with local entities, supporting the infrastructure and cultural initiatives that will contribute to more active civic engagement. By streamlining funding processes, simplifying bureaucratic hurdles, and fostering cross-sector collaboration, a more fluid relationship between the public and private sectors can emerge, enhancing the cultural landscape and broadening participation.

Key Ideas from Participants:

- Importance of **digital civic spaces**, recognising both their opportunities and the potential risks, such as the unregulated nature of online platforms. It was emphasised the need for rules and guidance to ensure these spaces remain productive and civil.
- Integration of **material and immaterial spaces**, noting that the responsibility of local authorities extends beyond just physical accessibility; it involves creating spaces that are culturally and socially inclusive, reflecting the community's diverse needs.
- Significance of **habit changes**, such as closing roads to cars, which can transform public spaces and cultural norms, making them more conducive to public engagement and social interaction.

To make this a reality, it will be crucial to balance **policy alignment, community involvement, and long-term planning**. Civic spaces must be designed not only to meet current needs but also to evolve with the times, accommodating future generations' methods of participation. The creation of these spaces will require continuous collaboration among all stakeholders, ensuring that the community's voice is central to the planning process.

The discussion has underscored the importance of **inclusive, adaptable, and dynamic civic spaces**, both digital and physical. The interconnectedness of these two realms presents a unique opportunity to create a robust, integrated civic space where all forms of participation, from online engagement to in-person interaction, are valued equally.

As the municipality of Torres Vedras and other local entities continue to engage with these challenges, it is clear that their collective actions will play a pivotal role in shaping a **plural, equitable, intergenerational, and culturally vibrant civic space**, one that is truly reflective of the democratic principles it aims to uphold.

In conclusion, the implementation of these proposals might be important for the development of a more cohesive and unified community. A well-coordinated civic space, where all voices are heard and all members of society can actively engage, is the ideal foundation for the exercise of democracy. This future will be pluralistic, equitable, intergenerational, and culturally vibrant, paving the way for a territory where everyone has a stake in shaping the shared public good.

1.2 B. RIGHT SPACES in Barcelona

Overview	
<p><i>A brief overview that presents: the key points discussed, the objections and critical points, the proposed actions</i></p>	
<p>The two sessions held on November 23rd addressed key issues related to the management of public space, community culture and the fight against hate speech. Collective experiences and diagnoses were shared that demonstrate the need for a more just and community-based city model. Actions were proposed to democratize the use of spaces and culture was highlighted as a tool for social transformation. Among the critical points, the privatisation of public space, the stigmatisation of groups and the lack of institutional recognition appeared. Data was collected through collective observations, working groups and shared reflections.</p> <p>The sessions on May 22nd, May 30th and June 5th, 2025, have allowed for a deeper understanding of the legal, administrative and practical avenues for public-community collaboration, as well as their application to municipalities. They have brought together representatives of the public administration, community entities and legal experts.</p> <p>The key points addressed have been the need for a new regulatory framework, the tensions with current legislation (such as the Contracts Law), the lack of recognition of common goods, and the experiences that demonstrate that other forms of management are possible.</p> <p>Among the proposed actions, the modification of legal frameworks, the development of instruments such as agreements, social agreements and delegated management, and the need for indicators that measure social return and use value stand out.</p>	
1. Introduction	
<p>Brief context of the sessions</p>	<p>The sessions took place on November 23 at the Pou de la Figuera community centre (Barcelona), with the participation of 49 people representing 25 community spaces. They were facilitated by the Punt 6 Collective and other agents such as Mariona Soler, Arnau Galí and Edna Rojas. The objective was to debate the management of public space and the role of community culture in the face of fascism.</p> <p>The main topics were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The impact of the city-spectacle model. • Unequal access to public space. • Cultural resistance to hate speech. • Community autonomy and democratic resilience. <p>The other sessions took place between May 22 and June 5, 2025, both online and in person (Barcelona and Manresa). Third sector entities, municipal technicians and public institutions participated. The facilitations were carried out by Mariona Soler, Claudia Delso and IDRA.</p> <p>Main topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public-community collaboration: definition, challenges and opportunities. • Interpretation and application of Law 9/2017 on Contracts.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of administrative law as a tool for transformation. • Territorial experiences of community management. • Role of local entities in promoting new models.
Overview of how the data was collected	<p>Data was collected through open discussions, shared diagnoses and collective reflections. Methodologies such as mind maps and working groups were used.</p> <p>Methodologies such as presentations of experiences, legal debates, group dynamics and round tables have been used.</p>
2. Main findings	
Thematic area 1	<p>Use and governance of public space</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unequal use of space (some entities can use it without permits). • Stigmatisation of spaces and groups (young people, racialised). • Difficulty consolidating community due to atomisation. • Lack of institutional recognition towards community management.
Thematic area 2	<p>Community culture as a tool against fascism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culture is key to democratic resilience. • Community work allows us to combat individualism and racism. • The need to build an open, committed and critical community is evident.
Thematic area 3	<p>Legal and administrative framework</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law 9/2017 on Contracts limits non-contractual formulas. • The new Catalan Law on the Promotion of Associations and Decree 69/2020 open the way for social concerts and delegated management. • The legal framework does not yet recognise common goods or community practices as specific figures.
Thematic area 4	<p>Role of municipalities and public innovation. Alliances and co-responsibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a growing willingness among local entities to seek alternatives to classic public procurement. • Examples such as Can Batlló, L'Obradora or the Ateneu de Salt demonstrate that community management focused on the common good is viable. • Public-community collaboration contributes to resilience and collective intelligence.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need to generate mutual trust and co-responsibility structures between administration and communities is evident. • A change in political and administrative culture is needed to give space to citizen co-production.
3. Challenges and barriers: Summary of the main challenges identified	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rigid regulations and unequal criteria according to districts. • Slowness and administrative bureaucracy. • Difficulty in accessing the space for non-formalized entities. • Absence of community fabric due to neighbourhood rotation and lack of generational succession. • Social fracture, individualism, fear, aporophobia and discriminatory discourses • Restrictive application of the Contracts Law by technicians. • Lack of specific legal categories for community management. • Absence of a stable regulatory framework that regulates public-community collaboration. • Legal uncertainty, especially in small municipalities. • Gap between technical knowledge and community reality. 	
4. Opportunities and strengths: Summary of the positive aspects or enabling factors observed	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of horizontal models of participation (self-management). • Recognition of the community as a fabric of resistance and memory. • Spaces of coexistence and diversity as a transformative political tool. • High perception of the value of community spaces. • The new ESS Law and other regulations are beginning to recognise community management. • Municipalities can lead innovation processes with tools such as agreements, social agreements or concerted action. • European frameworks (such as the Pact of Amsterdam) endorse citizen participation as key to public policies. • There is growing recognition of the value of the community in emergency situations and in the sustainability of services. 	
5. Proposals and recommendations: Proposed strategies and actions classified by priority or schedule (short, medium, long term...)	
<p>Short term</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of bureaucratic self-defence tools and legal advice. • Protocols against hate speech and aggression. • Training for technicians on existing legal loopholes. • Develop practical guides on tenders adapted to community collaboration. • Preparation of legal reports that support the flexibility of the Contracts Law. <p>Medium term</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective management of permits and infrastructures. • Visibility of the social and cultural value of spaces. 	

- Promote legislative reforms such as the modification of the Barcelona Municipal Charter.
- Create a network of community services with formal recognition.
- Work with the Provincial Council and municipal associations to define coordination frameworks.

Long term

- Formal recognition of community management.
- Promotion of new indicators that reflect public-community value.
- Transformation of community spaces into schools of democracy and participation.
- Develop a new Catalan law on public-community collaboration.
- Expand the Generalitat's portfolio of services to include community services.
- Establish social return indicators focused on the common good.

6. Possible future activities to protect, promote and support civic space in the territory

<p>Action plan, responsibilities, deadlines</p>	<p>Development of an action plan and a collective Manifesto generated by the Community Spaces network.</p> <p>Consolidation of alliances between spaces for joint actions.</p> <p>Continuous training in anti-fascism, social rights and participatory management.</p> <p>Development of framework agreements and clause specifications with community criteria.</p> <p>Creation of a good practices guide for public-community collaboration.</p> <p>Strategic alliances with the third sector to strengthen political advocacy.</p> <p>Creation of an observatory of good practices in community management.</p>
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7. Conclusion: Final remarks and next steps

The sessions served to collectively diagnose the limitations of current public space and the need to transform it from the ground up. The role of community spaces as key agents for democracy and social justice was reinforced. The proposed path is one of creative resistance, community articulation and daily political action.

The sessions have allowed for the building of shared knowledge between technicians, entities and lawyers on the limits and opportunities of the current framework. Public-community collaboration is presented as a possible and desirable way to guarantee a more participatory, rooted and fair public service.

The path forward includes regulatory impetus, training, practice and the generation of collaborative tools. This process is a commitment to a more radical, situated and transformative democracy.

1.3 B. RIGHT SPACES in Warsaw

Overview	
<p>Civic spaces, such as Local Activity Centres (Miejsca Aktywności Lokalnej, MALs), play a crucial role in fostering social cohesion, democratic participation, and a sense of belonging at the neighbourhood level. In recent years, Warsaw has developed a rich and diverse network of such spaces, providing residents with opportunities to engage in local initiatives, build relationships, and respond to shared challenges.</p> <p>Foundation for Social and Economic Initiatives (FISE) conducted a series of policy labs dedicated to examining the condition and potential of civic spaces in Warsaw, with a particular focus on Local Activity Centres (Miejsca Aktywności Lokalnej, MALs). These sessions aimed to collect insights, identify challenges, and propose improvements for enhancing civic engagement and strengthening local communities. As part of the policy lab procesem, FISE organized a series of meetings involving key stakeholders, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representatives of the City of Warsaw (municipal officials and decision-makers), • Coordinators and managers of civic spaces across the city, • Local residents and grassroots activists who co-create and regularly participate in MAL activities. 	
1. Introduction	
<p>Brief background of the sessions</p>	<p>Participants:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. City Officials and Municipal Representatives <p>Representatives from social department of the City of Warsaw participated in the policylab, including those responsible for social policy, civic engagement and civic Spaces. Their input was crucial for understanding the institutional context in which MALs operate, including funding mechanisms, policy frameworks, and strategic priorities for civic infrastructure.</p> 2. Coordinators and Managers of Local Activity Centres <p>These individuals are responsible for the day-to-day management and programming of MALs. They shared practical insights into the needs of their communities, organisational challenges, and successful engagement strategies. Many expressed the need for greater institutional support and more autonomy in shaping the direction of their spaces. We meet with representatives of: Grójecka 109 MAL, Dwa Jelonki MAL, Partnerstwo Sadyba, Partnerstwo Jazdów, MAL w DPS Bielany, 3 Pokoje z kuchnią, Dom Kultury Praga MAL.</p> 3. Community Members and Grassroots Activists <p>People who regularly participate in or co-create civic spaces provided firsthand accounts of what MALs mean to them. Participants included neighbourhood residents, local leaders, volunteers and members of informal groups. Their contributions highlighted the social value of MALs as spaces for connection, support, and empowerment.</p>

	<p>4. Representatives of NGOs and Partner Organisations</p> <p>Non-governmental organisations that collaborate with MALs or operate similar community-oriented projects also took part in the discussions. They contributed perspectives on sustainability, inclusive practices, and the potential for network-building between different civic actors in the city.</p>
<p>Overview of how data were collected</p>	<p>To ensure the policy labs were inclusive, dynamic, and grounded in the real experiences of those involved in civic spaces, FISE applied a variety of participatory and co-creative methods. These approaches helped gather diverse perspectives, stimulate collaborative thinking, and collectively shape visions for the future of civic infrastructure in Warsaw. Below is an overview of the key methods used during the process:</p> <p>1. Thematic Working Groups</p> <p>Participants were divided into smaller groups focused on specific themes. This method allowed for more in-depth conversations, encouraged peer learning, and ensured that diverse voices were heard on each topic. Thematic groups were moderated by facilitator who helped structure the discussions and synthesize key takeaways.</p> <p>2. Mind Mapping</p> <p>Mind mapping exercises were used to visually explore the needs, assets, and challenges of civic spaces. Participants created shared maps on paper or whiteboards, identifying connections between stakeholders, resources, and barriers. This method helped make complex systems more understandable and revealed hidden relationships and dependencies.</p> <p>3. Future Search</p> <p>As a forward-looking exercise, FISE adapted elements of the Future Search methodology—a participatory planning tool designed to align diverse stakeholders around a shared vision of the future. Participants reflected on past experiences, analyzed current trends, and co-created possible futures for civic spaces in Warsaw. This structured process encouraged long-term thinking and fostered a sense of shared responsibility for next steps.</p> <p>4. Roundtable Discussions</p> <p>Several policy labs were conducted as roundtables, where participants from different sectors—public officials, community leaders, NGOs, and citizens—engaged in open dialogue on equal footing. These sessions promoted mutual understanding, built trust, and allowed for the exchange of institutional and grassroots perspectives.</p> <p>5. Creative cards</p> <p>One of the key tools used during the sessions were creative cards. These cards served as prompts to stimulate dialogue, imagination, and critical thinking. The cards were tailored to different stages of the workshops, for example:</p> <p>Vision cards supported the imagining of future possibilities and alternative models of civic engagement.</p>

	<p>Cards for Identifying Strengths of Civic Spaces</p> <p>These cards were used to help participants recognise and articulate what already works well in civic spaces such as Local Activity Centres (MALs). Participants used them to reflect on examples from their own experiences, map the strengths present in their own context, and discuss how these qualities can be nurtured or scaled.</p> <p>The exercise created space for appreciative inquiry, allowing people to focus not only on problems but also on the value civic spaces bring to communities. It helped shift the conversation from scarcity and struggle to resilience and possibility.</p> <p>Cards for Exploring Personal Motivation and Purpose</p> <p>Another set of cards was designed to help participants reflect on why they choose to engage in social and civic work. These cards included open-ended prompts such as:</p> <p>“I care about my community because...”</p> <p>“What drives me to act is...”</p> <p>“A moment I felt that this work mattered was...”</p> <p>“The change I want to see is...”</p> <p>This part of the workshop invited personal storytelling and values-based reflection, helping participants connect their everyday work to deeper sources of meaning. It also created an opportunity to recognise the emotional and ethical dimensions of civic engagement, something that is often overlooked in strategic or policy-level discussions.</p> <p>Using these cards in group settings encouraged participants to share personal motivations, build empathy, and strengthen a sense of common purpose.</p>
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2. Main findings

<p>Thematic Area 1: What supports civic spaces in Warsaw – political and legal conditions conducive to the development of civic spaces.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Direct financial support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open grant competitions. • City Hall runs annual competitions where NGOs and community groups can apply for funding to operate civic spaces or organize activities in them. • Regranting mechanisms • The city entrusts umbrella organisations to redistribute smaller grants (microgrants) to neighbourhood groups and informal initiatives. This simplifies access to funds for grassroots actors. • Multi-year funding • Some programs (e.g. running MALs or long-term cultural programs) receive 3-year financing, which supports stability and long-term planning. 2. Provision of infrastructure and space <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free or low-cost access to municipal premises • City Hall facilitates access to public buildings such as: • Schools after hours
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Libraries • Cultural centres • Dedicated MAL locations • Civic actors can use these spaces for meetings, workshops, exhibitions, and social events. • Support in adapting or co-designing spaces • In some cases, the city co-finances renovations or helps adapt facilities for civic use (e.g. accessibility upgrades, equipment, furniture). <p>3. Institutional coordination and mentoring</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated municipal departments • The Centrum Komunikacji Społecznej (CKS) coordinates policies and support mechanisms for civil society, including MALs, consultations, and civic education. • MAL network coordination • The city funds a central coordination office that provides MAL operators with tools, communication support, training, and evaluation tools. • Legal and organisational guidance • City officials often assist NGOs in navigating legal and administrative requirements (permits, accounting, contracts). <p>4. Promotion, visibility and outreach</p> <p>The city actively promotes civic participation through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Websites like www.mal.um.warszawa.pl • Social media campaigns and printed guides to local spaces • Events such as Warszawski Tydzień Lokalności (Warsaw Locality Week), showcasing local initiatives • Co-branded civic identity • Many civic spaces use visual identity provided by the city, which adds legitimacy and makes them recognisable to residents. <p>5. Policy-level inclusion and strategic alignment</p> <p>Civic spaces are integrated into city strategies, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warszawa 2030 Strategy • Program for Cooperation with NGOs • Diversity and Inclusion Policy (supporting minority and migrant access to civic life) • The city uses evaluation tools (surveys, participatory panels, MAL network reports) to adjust policies based on resident needs.
<p>Threats and challenges faced by civic spaces in Warsaw.</p>	<p>1. Unstable or short-term funding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many MALs operate on yearly or project-based grants, making it difficult to plan long-term, retain staff, or invest in infrastructure. • Lack of multi-year financial security limits the sustainability and growth of community programs. <p>2. Overlapping bureaucracy and unclear procedures</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinators often face complex administrative processes for funding, reporting, or using public spaces (e.g., schools or parks). • Unclear legal status of some civic activities (e.g., informal groups using public buildings) can cause friction or delays. <p>3. Staff burnout and low compensation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAL coordinators frequently report work overload, managing both coordination and facilitation with limited support. • Salaries are often too low to attract or retain qualified staff with social or educational expertise. <p>4. Lack of visibility and public awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many local residents are unaware that MALs exist or misunderstand their purpose (e.g., confusing them with cultural centres or municipal offices). • Limited budgets for promotion and outreach reduce civic engagement and participation. <p>5. Limited accessibility or inclusivity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some MALs are located in buildings that are not fully accessible (e.g., no elevators, poor signage), limiting participation by elderly, people with disabilities, or migrants. • Coordinators also highlight the need for multilingual materials and better support for culturally diverse residents. <p>6. Inadequate infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some civic spaces lack basic equipment or appropriate conditions for workshops and meetings. • Shared spaces (culture house) may have restricted access hours or usage limitations. <p>7. Tensions with local authorities or institutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In some districts, there is resistance from public institutions to host civic activities. <p>8. Political or ideological pressures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinators express concern about potential politicisation of civic spaces or growing scrutiny from ideologically motivated actors. • There is a risk of civic activities being questioned or blocked if seen as “too progressive” or critical of authorities.
<p>Good practices in civic spaces in Warsaw</p> <p>Method: Appreciate Workshop</p>	<p>Good Practices in Local Activity Centres (MAL) in Warsaw – Based on Appreciate Workshop</p> <p>During the Appreciate Workshop, coordinators and participants identified several good practices that reflect the values of inclusion, empowerment, and co-creation. Here are a few standout examples:</p> <p>1. Co-creation with Local Residents</p>

	<p>Practice: Many MALs have adopted a model where programs and activities are co-designed with the local community, not just delivered to them.</p> <p>Example: At MAL 3pokoje z kuchnią, monthly planning sessions invite local residents to suggest ideas and co-lead events (cooking, art walks, repair cafés).</p> <p>Example 2: The Sadyba Partnership is a living example of how grassroots cooperation, with light coordination and shared values, can activate a neighbourhood. The partnership organizes regular events aimed at strengthening neighbourhood ties, such as:</p> <p>“Neighbour’s Day” (Dzień Sąsiada) – open-air picnics with music, games, local food, and community-run stands.</p> <p>Seasonal events – like Christmas decoration workshops or spring planting days.</p> <p>Neighbourhood walks and history tours – promoting local heritage and intergenerational storytelling.</p> <p>Why it works: Builds ownership and trust. People are more engaged when they feel they co-create the space.</p> <p>2. Open Door Policy</p> <p>Practice: MALs emphasise openness—no need for membership, prior registration, or formal affiliation.</p> <p>Example: MAL Kotłownia operates as a drop-in space where residents can come in to talk, use materials, start spontaneous initiatives, or simply be together in a welcoming environment.</p> <p>Why it works: Reduces barriers to entry for marginalized or hesitant participants (e.g. seniors, migrants, isolated individuals).</p> <p>3. Intercultural and Inclusive Programming</p> <p>Practice: MALs run events that foster dialogue between different cultural, age, and social groups.</p> <p>Example: At MAL Grójecka 109, Ukrainian and Polish families co-organized bilingual storytelling sessions. Coordinators invited migrant women to co-lead sessions to ensure relevance.</p> <p>Why it works: Promotes social integration and mutual learning in a safe, shared space.</p> <p>4. Use of Creative and Participatory Methods</p> <p>Practice: MALs use non-formal education methods like storytelling, open space technology, and artistic workshops to spark engagement.</p> <p>Example: An “Appreciation Wall” was created during the workshop to visually collect what people value in MAL Grójecka 109.</p> <p>This inspired MAL staff to replicate the idea locally as a form of community feedback.</p> <p>Why it works: Interactive and creative methods lower psychological barriers and promote deeper dialogue.</p> <p>5. Reflection and Peer Learning</p>
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	<p>Practice: Coordinators meet regularly (e.g. during the Appreciate Workshop or city-wide MAL meetups) to share what works, troubleshoot issues, and exchange tools.</p>
<p>Recommendations for civic spaces in Warsaw. Method: Future Search</p>	<p>Future Search Workshop Outcomes:</p> <p>Recommendations for the Democratic and Sustainable Development of Civic Spaces in Warsaw</p> <p>Background</p> <p>During a recent Future Search workshop, diverse stakeholders, including MAL coordinators, local activists, city officials, and residents, came together to envision how Warsaw’s civic spaces can grow in ways that strengthen democracy and promote sustainability. The process emphasised shared understanding, joint commitment, and practical steps for the future.</p> <p>One important insight from the workshop was how challenging it was for participants to look optimistically toward the future without first continuously diagnosing and discussing existing problems. While the Future Search method encourages forward-thinking and collective visioning, many felt the need to acknowledge ongoing difficulties, such as funding instability, bureaucratic hurdles, and social exclusion, before fully embracing long-term planning. This highlighted the importance of balancing problem analysis with hopeful, solution-oriented dialogue to create realistic and sustainable paths forward for civic spaces in Warsaw.</p> <p>Key Recommendations</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure Long-Term and Stable Funding <p>Participants agreed that reliable, multi-year funding is essential. This stability would allow civic spaces to plan strategically, retain skilled staff, and expand inclusive programs without constant financial uncertainty.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Enhance Accessibility and Inclusivity <p>Physical accessibility (ramps, elevators, signage) and cultural-linguistic inclusivity (multilingual materials, diverse programming) should be prioritized to ensure all residents can engage meaningfully.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Strengthen Collaboration with Local Authorities <p>A recurring theme during the workshop was the essential role of mutual trust in the success and sustainability of civic spaces. For many participants, civic spaces function best when they are rooted in trust between the citizen and the space, where residents feel welcome, respected, and empowered to act without fear of judgment or institutional control. This requires that civic spaces not only remain physically accessible, but also emotionally and socially safe, spaces of belonging and autonomy.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Equally important is the trust from public authorities toward civic spaces themselves. Participants emphasised the need for city institutions to grant civic spaces more freedom, flexibility, and respect in how they operate. This means moving away from overly rigid regulations, micromanagement, or excessive reporting, and

	<p>toward a model where civic actors are trusted as competent, responsible partners in shaping local life. Trust creates the conditions for innovation, experimentation, and responsiveness to community needs.</p> <p>5. Expand Capacity Building and Peer Learning</p> <p>Civic spaces thrive when the people who run them—coordinators, facilitators, volunteers, and local leaders—have opportunities to learn, grow, and support one another. Participants in the workshop emphasised that strengthening the competencies and confidence of these actors is essential for the long-term success of civic infrastructure in Warsaw.</p> <p>This means investing in regular training, mentoring, and skill-sharing, not just in technical areas (organizing events, grant writing, conflict resolution), but also in soft skills such as community facilitation, inclusive leadership, and responding to crises (supporting refugees, dealing with burnout).</p> <p>Equally important is creating horizontal networks of peer learning, spaces where MAL coordinators, NGO leaders, and active residents can meet, reflect, and exchange tools and experiences. These networks reduce isolation, inspire innovation, and help scale up successful practices across districts. Participants suggested formats such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-MAL study visits and shadowing programs Supervisions of MAL’s Coordinators Regular meetings of MAL Coordinators in the form of mutual learning and support preventing burn out <p>Workshop participants also highlighted the need for a more structured and accessible knowledge base, such as a shared digital platform with toolkits, guides, evaluation methods, and documentation of good practices, available to all civic actors.</p> <p>6. Increase Visibility and Outreach</p> <p>Strategic communication campaigns using social media, local media, and community networks are recommended to raise awareness of civic spaces’ roles and invite broader participation.</p>
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3. Challenges and barriers: Summary of major challenges identified

Civic spaces in Warsaw, especially Local Activity Centres (MALs), play an essential role in strengthening community bonds and local democracy. Despite their growing presence, they face several key challenges. The most significant is unstable, short-term funding, which limits long-term planning, staff retention, and program development. Coordinators often struggle with bureaucratic hurdles and complex procedures, while facing burnout due to excessive responsibilities and low compensation.

Public awareness of MALs remains low, and many residents are unaware of their purpose. Additionally, some spaces are not fully accessible (physically or culturally) making it harder for people with disabilities, migrants to participate. Infrastructure is often inadequate, with limited equipment or poor working conditions, and the level of support from local authorities varies widely between districts.

There are also concerns about political pressure, which can discourage bold or inclusive initiatives. These challenges underline the need for more stable funding, stronger institutional trust, and greater autonomy to ensure that civic spaces can continue to serve as inclusive and resilient centres of local life.

4. Opportunities and strengths: Summary of positive aspects or enabling factors observed

Local Activity Centres (MALs) are supported by a network of municipal and grassroots actors, these spaces benefit from direct public funding, including open grant competitions, regranteeing mechanisms, and multi-year financing, which allows for greater stability and long-term planning. The city also offers free or low-cost access to infrastructure such as schools, libraries, and cultural centres, and in some cases supports the adaptation of these spaces to better serve community needs. However participants in the policy labs pointed out that the costs of maintaining the spaces are too high for many initiatives, which means they cannot afford to run civic spaces. It is different in the case of MALs that operate within cultural institutions or social care centres (DPS), where conditions are more favorable.

Institutional coordination through dedicated departments and networks strengthens civic infrastructure, providing MALs with training, legal guidance, and evaluation tools. MALs also benefit from city-level promotional efforts that boost their visibility and help establish a recognisable civic identity. Strategic alignment with city policies, including the Warsaw 2030 Strategy and Diversity and Inclusion Policy, further anchors their role in long-term urban planning.

Crucially, the participatory methods used in FISE's policy labs, such as thematic groups, creative cards, and Future Search workshops, highlighted the unique strengths of these spaces. MALs are built on co-creation with residents, an open-door philosophy, and inclusive programming that reflects the diverse makeup of local communities. Good practices include intergenerational and intercultural events, peer learning among coordinators, and use of creative methods to spark engagement. These elements create spaces where people feel a strong sense of ownership, trust, and belonging.

Participants emphasised the importance of trust between civic actors and public institutions as a foundation for innovation and sustainable development. When empowered with autonomy, resources, and supportive networks, MALs can evolve into resilient civic hubs capable of responding to both everyday needs and larger social challenges. The process of appreciating existing strengths helped shift the narrative from problem-solving to possibility-thinking, affirming the role of MALs as one of Warsaw's most successful civic innovations.

5. Proposals and recommendations: Proposed strategies and actions categorised by priority or timeline (short-term, medium-term, long-term...)

Short-Term (0–1 year): Immediate Actions for Stabilisation and Visibility

1. **Secure Bridge Funding for Key MALs**
Provide temporary financial support to MALs operating on unstable annual grants to prevent service disruption and staff turnover.
2. **Improve Visibility and Outreach**
Launch a city-wide information campaign to increase public awareness of MALs, using social media, printed materials, and neighbourhood-level outreach in multiple languages.
3. **Remove Barriers to Accessibility**
Identify MALs with the most urgent infrastructural gaps (lack of ramps) and address these through small-scale upgrades.
4. **Develop a Digital Knowledge Platform**
Create an online, publicly accessible hub for civic actors, featuring guides, toolkits, event calendars, and good practice documentation.
5. **Simplify Administrative Processes**
Introduce clearer and more transparent guidelines for funding applications, reporting, and space usage, especially for grassroots groups.

Medium-Term (1–3 years): Strengthening Structures and Capacity

1. **Introduce Multi-Year Funding as the Norm**
Institutionalize three-year funding cycles for MALs and related civic initiatives to enable strategic planning, talent retention, and sustainable growth.
2. **Expand Capacity-Building Programs**
Offer regular training, mentoring, and peer learning opportunities for coordinators, facilitators, and active residents, covering topics such as inclusive leadership, conflict resolution, and community facilitation.
3. **Strengthen Inclusive Practices**
Develop multilingual and culturally sensitive materials, and co-design programs with underrepresented groups, such as migrants or people with disabilities.
4. **Promote Inter-MAL Collaboration**
Establish structured peer-learning formats, such as thematic working groups, inter-district study visits, and annual civic forums, to promote innovation and knowledge sharing across the network.
5. **Foster Emotional Safety and Autonomy**
Create safe environments where civic actors feel empowered, respected, and free from excessive oversight. Encourage open-door policies and co-created programming.

Long-Term (3–5+ years): Systemic Change and Sustainability

1. **Integrate Civic Spaces into Urban Planning**
Make civic infrastructure a core element of Warsaw's development plans, including housing policy, education, and sustainability strategies.
2. **Decentralize and Equalise Access**

	<p>Ensure an even distribution of well-funded MALs across all districts, particularly in underserved or peripheral areas.</p> <p>3. Institutionalise Participatory Governance</p> <p>Develop formal mechanisms for community input and co-decision-making in the management and future direction of civic spaces.</p> <p>4. Establish a Civic Trust Framework</p> <p>Reform regulations to reduce micromanagement and administrative burdens, creating a relationship of mutual trust between city authorities and civic actors.</p> <p>5. Evaluate and Scale What Works</p>
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6. Possible future activities to protect, promote, support civic space in the territory

<p>Plan of actions, responsibilities, deadlines</p>	<p>1. Protecting Civic Space</p> <p>Action 1.1 – Stabilise Financial Foundations of MALs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Ensure multi-year, predictable funding to reduce precarity and enable strategic development. • Responsible: City of Warsaw – Social Policy Department, Finance Department <p>Action 1.2 – Safeguard Autonomy and Freedom of Expression in Civic Spaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Develop guidelines that prevent political interference and protect the independence of MAL programming. • Responsible: City Council, MAL Coordination Unit, Legal Advisors <p>Action 1.2 – Ensure Equal Access Across the City</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Conduct a territorial audit to identify gaps in access to civic spaces (especially in underserved neighbourhoods). • Responsible: MAL Network Coordination, Urban Planning Department <p>2. Promoting Civic Space</p> <p>Action 2.1 – City-Wide Awareness Campaign</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Promote MALs through social media, public transportation ads, multilingual flyers, and local events. • Responsible: City Communications Office, MAL Coordination Unit <p>Action 2.2 – Celebrate Local Civic Innovation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Establish an annual “Civic Spaces Day” to showcase good practices and recognise community leaders. • Responsible: Office for Civil Society, NGOs, local media partners <p>Action 2.3 – Develop a Digital Hub for Civic Spaces</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Create a multilingual online platform with tools, guides, and event listings. • Responsible: MAL Network Coordination, IT Department, NGO partners <p>3. Supporting Civic Space</p> <p>Action 3.1 – Invest in Infrastructure and Accessibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Upgrade MAL facilities to meet accessibility and functionality standards (e.g., ramps, Wi-Fi, climate control). • Responsible: Municipal Infrastructure Department, Local District Offices <p>Action 3.2 – Develop a Civic Space Leadership Program</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Train and mentor MAL coordinators, volunteers, and local leaders in inclusive facilitation, conflict resolution, and co-creation. • Responsible: NGOs, Academic Institutions, MAL Coordination Office <p>Action 3.3 – Establish Peer Learning and Support Structures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Create working groups, learning retreats, and cross-district exchange programs for civic space actors. • Responsible: MAL Coordination Office, NGO Networks <p>Action 3.4 – Implement Participatory Evaluation Mechanisms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description: Engage community members in the evaluation and co-design of MAL services and goals. • Responsible: City of Warsaw, External Evaluators, Resident Panels
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7. Conclusion: Final remarks and next steps

Civic spaces in Warsaw, particularly Local Activity Centres (Miejsca Aktywności Lokalnej, MALs), have emerged as vital platforms for fostering community engagement, strengthening local democracy, and building social cohesion. Over recent years, the city has developed a dynamic and diverse network of such spaces, enabling residents to co-create local initiatives, develop relationships, and respond collectively to societal challenges.

Through a participatory process led by the Foundation for Social and Economic Initiatives (FISE), a series of policy labs was conducted to examine the current state, potential, and future of civic spaces in Warsaw. These labs brought together stakeholders: city officials, civic space coordinators, local residents, NGOs, and grassroots activists. Using creative and inclusive tools, including thematic working groups, mind mapping, future-search workshops, and specially designed reflection cards, the process generated a comprehensive understanding of strengths, gaps, and aspirations for the future.

Findings from the labs revealed a rich landscape of positive practices already taking place within MALs: from co-created programs and intercultural events to open-door policies and innovative peer learning formats. These practices demonstrate the unique value of civic spaces as welcoming, empowering, and adaptable platforms for community life.

At the same time, participants identified structural and operational barriers that hinder the full potential of civic spaces. These include unstable funding, bureaucratic complexity, staff burnout, limited visibility, and inadequate infrastructure. Addressing these challenges will require strategic

and long-term investment from the city, alongside a commitment to decentralisation, trust-building, and meaningful partnerships with civil society.

As part of the collective visioning process, stakeholders proposed a roadmap for democratic and sustainable development of civic spaces in Warsaw. Prioritized actions include securing long-term funding, improving physical and cultural accessibility, expanding leadership development programs, strengthening networks of cooperation, and enhancing visibility through targeted outreach campaigns.

1.4 B. RIGHT SPACES in Turin

Overview	
<p>The Policy Lab in Turin, promoted within the framework of the European project B.RIGHT SPACES, involved over 60 local stakeholders to explore the role of civic spaces as urban democratic infrastructures through a participatory process based on interviews, focus groups, and workshops.</p> <p>Among the enabling factors, the process highlighted the organisational flexibility and hybridisation capacity of civic spaces, which are able to connect culture, social life, economy, participation and inclusion. Equally essential is shared management, which strengthens the sense of belonging and collective responsibility, as well as the presence of relational ecosystems rooted in local neighbourhoods, fostering collaboration and proximity. Some key figures, such as facilitators, cultural mediators, and community managers, play a crucial role in bridging needs, languages, and resources.</p> <p>However, alongside these resources, several structural barriers were identified. These include asymmetries in the relationships with public institutions, lack of formal and professional recognition for key roles, disproportionate administrative and bureaucratic pressures, economic fragility, and limited communication visibility, all of which undermine long-term sustainability. Additionally, there are access barriers for specific social groups (particularly youth, women, and migrants) and gender disparities persist, along with issues related to the quality and safety of physical spaces.</p> <p>Based on these findings, the Policy Lab outlined a set of challenges and proposals to strengthen the potential of civic spaces. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the acknowledgement of civic spaces as political actors and generators of public policies; • the valorisation of hybrid competences and facilitating roles; • the promotion of collaborative governance models and co-decision-making tools; • the identification of themes such as culture, digitalisation, and proximity-based welfare as key assets for innovation and bottom-up participation; • the enhancement of integrated territorial ecosystems, capable of supporting connections between public institutions, private actors, and active citizenship. 	
1. Introduction	
<p>Brief background of the sessions</p>	<p>This document presents the outcomes of the <i>Turin Policy Lab</i> held within the framework of the B.RIGHT SPACES project, aimed at exploring the dynamics, challenges, and opportunities linked to civic spaces in urban contexts. The session was conceived as part of a broader European initiative fostering mutual learning pathways through locally rooted participatory processes.</p> <p>In Turin, the Policy Lab brought together a diverse range of stakeholders—including local institutions, civil society organisations, NGOs, research and education bodies, and active citizens—with the aim of collectively reflecting on the factors that enable or inhibit the development and sustainability of vibrant civic spaces.</p> <p>Building on the city’s longstanding experience with participatory governance, particularly through the Network of Neighbourhood Houses (NoNH), the Municipality of Turin collaborated with Labsus and Torino Social Impact to focus this path on evaluating active</p>

	<p>participation mechanisms and extending civic engagement practices beyond the existing framework. The initiative sought to capitalize on existing evaluation systems used by the NoNH to measure social impact, while also engaging civic actors operating outside the network to gather a more plural and representative picture of local civic spaces.</p> <p>The overarching goals of this Policy Lab were to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) related to civic spaces in the city; ● Explore how to adapt local governance conditions to better support civic ecosystems; ● Enhance collective knowledge of effective approaches and tools for protecting and evolving civic spaces. <p>Ultimately, the Turin Policy Labs aimed to support the creation of a metropolitan community of practice, strengthening the role of civic spaces as democratic infrastructures and enabling mutual learning among diverse actors in the city.</p> <p>Participants and Stakeholders</p> <p>The participatory process intentionally included a broad range of actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Civil society organisations (CSOs) and NGOs ● Social economy actors and cooperatives ● Civic space managers and pacts for collaboration ● Philanthropic foundations and funding bodies ● City and regional administration representatives ● Research and education institutions ● Individual citizens and activists
<p>Overview of how data were collected</p>	<p>The Turin Policy Lab adopted a participatory and multi-stakeholder approach to gather qualitative insights into the state and future of civic spaces in the city. The methodology was designed to ensure the inclusion of diverse voices and institutional levels, combining a mix of focus groups, thematic workshops, and individual interviews, each connected to broader public programs and civic events.</p> <p>Engagement Framework</p> <p>The consultation process involved over 65 participants across four main sessions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1st Focus Group (4 March 2025): Conducted with the Steering Committee of the Network of Neighbourhood Houses (NoNH), this session gathered 20 participants at Palazzo Civico, including Deputy Mayors, representatives from various departments of the Municipality of Turin and several Neighbourhood Houses. The objective was to assess the strengths, critical issues, and opportunities of the Houses model, with a particular focus on the latest social impact evaluation cycles (2022–2024).

- **1st Workshop** (2 April 2025): Organized within the framework of the **Democracy Biennale**, this session brought together 19 participants from third-sector organisations, civic spaces, philanthropic institutions, and active citizens at **BeeOzanam community hub**. The workshop explored enablers and obstacles to active participation, particularly among youth, and discussed experiences from the broader civic ecosystem in Turin.
- **2nd Workshop** (16 May 2025): Held during the **Turin International Book Fair**, this workshop (25 participants) re-engaged both municipal actors and independent civic stakeholders. It built on previous discussions and expanded on reflections from the NoNH's latest impact assessment, aiming to identify system-level challenges and opportunities in promoting democratic access to civic infrastructure.
- **2nd Focus Group** (29 May 2025): A final online session with four **local and regional experts**—including researchers, administrators, and civic innovation leaders—served as a **validation round** for emerging findings. Discussions focused on translating local observations into concrete **recommendations for local policy guidelines** and potential contributions to the future **EU Charter for the Defenders of Civic Spaces**.

In addition to these events, an **in-depth interview** was conducted with a NoNH project manager (16 May 2025), offering a focused narrative on the internal mechanisms and participation dynamics within the Neighbourhood Houses network.

Through the participatory pathway of the Turin Policy Labs, over 60 stakeholders were actively involved, offering a diverse range of insights into the condition and evolution of civic spaces across the city. A key result of this process has been the construction of a **broader understanding of civic participation**, especially from the perspective of civic spaces that operate outside the formal framework of the Neighbourhood Houses Network (NoNH).

Participants helped surface critical questions that structured the reflection:

- What mechanisms of civic engagement are most effective?
- How are marginalized groups represented in civic spaces?
- What are the primary obstacles and threats facing civic participation today?
- What emerging challenges must be addressed to enable more sustainable and inclusive participation?

The discussions also focused on **supporting policies and bottom-up strategies** capable of reinforcing civic spaces while reducing their vulnerabilities. In particular, the analysis conducted at the local level with a broad network of civic spaces in Turin highlighted the importance of interpreting civic participation through the lens of **Henri Lefebvre's "right to the city"** (Lefebvre, 1972) —a concept that resonates with key principles in the *European Charter of Fundamental Rights*:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the right to public and common space, as a place for free expression, and for civic and political engagement; • the right to social interaction and access to culture; • the right to social well-being, as well as to beauty; • the right to fair work and just economies. <p>From this framework, three thematic areas emerged, reflecting different yet overlapping ways civic spaces contribute to democracy and active participation in Turin (See Next box)</p>
2. Main findings	
<p>Thematic Area 1: Civic spaces as arenas for active participation in the care of the commons and in local public decision-making processes</p>	<p>In this dimension, civic participation is primarily understood as <i>community activation</i>, rooted in solidarity, care for the commons, and <i>proximity welfare</i>. Here, participation often materialises as collective efforts for the general interest, community-based mutual aid, social and cultural initiatives, and participatory governance of the spaces themselves.</p> <p>Key insights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strength: These civic spaces are often institutionally recognised, forming alliances with public administrations. • Opportunity: They can engage in co-programming and co-design with local authorities, especially when linked to NoN. • Challenge: Enhance the role of civic spaces as promoters of community life, ensuring that the expansion of their functions through the provision of public services does not undermine their original mission or the sustainability of their resources and competencies.
<p>Thematic Area 2: Civic spaces as hubs of political activism and value-driven action</p>	<p>In this area, participation is shaped by shared values and activist engagement, centred on the defense of civil rights: gender equality, anti-fascism, and minority protections. These civic spaces act as cultural and political catalysts, fostering discourse and mobilisation.</p> <p>Key insights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strength: These spaces often function as informal and independent cultural centres, flexible and dynamic. • Opportunity: They tend to attract young, politically engaged communities, where the boundaries between activist and user are fluid. • Challenge: These spaces experience weaker or fragmented relationships with institutions, leading to potential isolation and reduced policy influence.
<p>Thematic Area 3: Civic spaces as drivers of civic economies and equitable labor</p>	<p>This cross-cutting area explores the economic dimension of civic spaces, especially their role in developing sustainable, impact-oriented models that align with their values.</p> <p>Key insights and open questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civic economies and civic spaces: How can civic spaces

	<p>balance economic self-sufficiency (through business activities) with their social mission?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Civic economies and civic spaces: What strategies can ensure durability (and autonomy/independence), especially in contexts with limited or unstable public funding? ● Labor conditions: How can civic spaces ensure fair labour conditions, ensuring consistency between their ethical values and the rights of workers? ● The power of networks: What role can networks play in creating stronger collective representation and institutional dialogue? <p>Together, these findings underscore the multiplicity of civic space models in Turin and the importance of developing tailored policies that respect their diversity while promoting shared values of democracy, inclusion, and collaboration.</p>
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3. Challenges and barriers: Summary of major challenges identified

HINDERING FACTORS

Relationship with public bodies:

- **Asymmetry in relationships with public authorities:** in the case of more informal and non-networked spaces, limited negotiation power for those working in civic spaces funded by public entities, even though there are opportunities to participate in discussions.
- **Administrative pressure:** high workloads and demands that are often misaligned with actual capacities.
- **Perception that more institutionalized spaces become less accessible.**
- **Lack of professional recognition:** key roles such as facilitators or community makers are neither acknowledged nor funded.
- **Outsourcing of services: in some civic spaces, risk of undermining civic functions and reducing the autonomy of those working in the spaces.**
- **Inadequate spaces:** poorly maintained or unwelcoming buildings, difficulties related to space renovation.

Communication:

- **Poor communication and visibility:** many citizens are unaware of civic spaces; they are often better known at the city level than in their own neighbourhoods.
- **Lack of a shared language.**
- **Ambiguity surrounding the definition of self-organisation:** not always recognised as a valuable process.
- **Lack of literacy and awareness on digital tools** for enabling civic spaces

Exclusion of social groups:

- **Dominance of established groups:** exclusion of new actors and diversity.
- **Exclusion of young people:** perception of inaccessibility to power and responsibility. "Participation is not yet a free and conscious choice."

- **Gender disparities in the workplace:** in loosely structured spaces democratic management, in term on economic sustainability can be more difficult.
- **When spaces are tied to a strong identity, many groups are excluded.** At the same time, the pressure to be exhaustive and inclusive of every target group can limit action and frustrate those seeking to strengthen social and cultural spaces.

Sustainability:

- **Gap between active citizenship, the civil economy ecosystem, civic responsibility, and entrepreneurship.**
- **Funding bodies often make requests** that are not aligned with the actions that subjects would like promote

Main Challenges

- Guarantee **autonomy and professional dignity** in civic spaces.
- **Renovate facilities** without compromising daily activities.
- Make spaces genuinely **inclusive and open to all groups.**
- **Recognise and formalize participation-related professions** in a stable way.
- Create effective and accessible **communication to** reach diverse audiences.
- Build a balance between institutionalisation and accessibility.
- Promote **youth participation as a free and conscious choice.**
- Ensure economic sustainability while respecting local identities.
- Avoid competition among social entities, fostering collaboration instead.
- Recognise and support self-organisation processes as a shared cultural asset.

4. Opportunities and strengths: Summary of positive aspects or enabling factors observed

This section explores the key factors that enable civic spaces to function as inclusive, democratic, and transformative urban infrastructures. Drawing from the interlocutions opened throughout the policy lab, civic spaces are revealed not only as physical places but also as **process-oriented ecosystems** that foster community, care, and social innovation.

Hereafter, a synthesis of the main results in terms of Enabling Factors and Opportunities.

ENABLING FACTORS

Physical Space as a Platform for facilitating social relations through non-exclusive use

- **Free and open** access for all, with no barriers or gatekeeping
- **Informal, flexible environments** that adapt to users' needs and are not necessarily linked with a specific function (you can enter, even if you are not "consuming")
- Quality design and **welcoming aesthetics** ("beautiful spaces")
- **Hybrid spaces**, where it is possible to find public facilities (i.e public shower- bagni pubblici) accessible to all and affordable social restaurants

Active Citizenship & Shared Governance

- **Participation** through both **usage** and **contribution** (time, skills, ideas)
- **80% of programming co-produced** with external groups, different from the subjects who directly manage the space (*terzietà dell'ente gestore*)

- Role of **civic space managers** as **enablers**, not controllers, not mainly programmers of the space
- **Formal tools and spaces to facilitate collaborative and equal settings, on both civic and institutional levels:** collaboration pacts, protocols with public authorities, but also open assemblies, participatory governance boards,

Autonomy & Economic Sustainability

- **Operational independence** in management and decision-making, especially in relations with public institutions
- **Figures who can act as 'provocateurs', activists that operate** to broaden the sense of civic space, its use, and the production of democracy, and actions oriented toward the public interest.
- **Stable multi-source funding:** public, private, philanthropic
- **Local partnerships** as strategic resources for sustainability, including P.A. and for-profit organisations
- Capacity to **adapt and maintain relevance** across political cycles, even though actions of lobbying and/or advocacy
- Capacity to lever on **social and solidarity economy projects**, such as “social restaurants”

Professional Facilitation & Capacity-Building

- Presence of **professional/trained staff to mediate, listen, and enable** citizen active contributions, but also dialogue with other community organisations, and public/private institutions (i.e p.a. and philanthropic bodies)
- **“Learning by doing”** as a mode of organisational development
- Support and **accompaniment for community-led projects** and informal groups
- Investment in **long-term capacitance** and **leadership** within the management group, also using employment **agreements that acknowledge and value** the complexity of the roles and competencies involved

Relational Ecosystems

- Strong emphasis on **trust, proximity, and dialogue:** civic spaces need to be rooted in their territory and community and grow/evolve following their evolutions
- Civic spaces as **hubs of cross-sector and intergenerational interaction**
- Civic spaces as **hubs for collaborative networks** with institutions, schools, associations, and activists
- **Culture and arts** as means to foster non-judgmental and inclusive environments for gathering subjects and people from different backgrounds.

Inclusive and Diverse Practices

- **Creation of “safe spaces”**, where participants can experience care to social, cultural, generational, and gender differences (i.e. steering groups to manage equality standards)
- **Spaces** not designed for one target, but **open to heterogeneity**
- **Tailored actions for youth**, including structured yet open programs
- **Informality as a key** to inclusion and organic community building

OPPORTUNITIES

Civic Innovation

- Civic spaces as **labs for urban welfare** and participatory governance
- Potential to **influence institutional policies** through **co-design and advocacy**, as being themselves concrete expressions of local communities, and/or being these places for active listening to communities needs and expectations.
- Hybrid and self-organized models for community social organisation, to **challenge traditional service delivery**

Social Infrastructure for Democracy

- Civic spaces as **defensible, non-controlled environments** for **spontaneous social gathering and recreational activities**, where it is possible to find opportunities to **political expression** and **mobilisation**
- Safe, accessible, and **relational spaces countering urban insecurity narratives**
- **Strengthen collective agency** and **local democracy**
- **Strengthen generative interpolation between digital and physical environments**

Urban-Rural Collaboration

- Opportunity to build **alliances** with rural or peri-urban actors
- **Shared learnings** between different territorial dynamics

New Forms of Recognition

- **Institutional frameworks** (e.g., interdepartmental governance tables) that recognise **civic spaces as part of urban policy**
- **Protocols** that formalize relationships **without suppressing flexibility**
- Regarding the theme of encounter, **art and culture can foster processes of meeting** that are diverse, non-judgmental, and free from rigid frameworks. There is a need for environments that allow us to “step outside ourselves and connect with others.”

Challenges to Address

- **Long-term financial sustainability** and policy backing
- Navigating between **formal recognition and bureaucratic overregulation**
- Ensuring **autonomy** while maintaining effective **partnerships**
- Balancing **structured programming** with **informal openness**
- Maintaining **adaptability** and **innovation** in shifting political environments
- **Digitalisation** as a not enough explored way to foster civic spaces

5. Proposals and recommendations: Proposed strategies and actions categorised by priority or timeline (short-term, medium-term, long-term...)

PROPOSAL

1. **Reinforcing the role of civic spaces as political actors and policy-making tools**

- Acknowledge civic spaces (e.g. *Case del Quartiere*, collaboration pacts, Hangar Piemonte) as active players in the **co-creation of public policies**.
 - Establish **structured mechanisms of dialogue between public institutions and civic spaces**, enabling the latter to be not only users but **co-producers of policies**.
2. **Re-centre social economy as a foundation for territorial sustainability**
 - Adopt the social economy as a **core principle** to reshape relationships between individuals, communities, and institutions.
 - Promote a **territorial development model** in which economic, social, and civic sustainability revolves around **the individual as the activating subject**.
 3. **Foster self-organisation mechanisms**
 - Provide **systems of opportunity** (regulatory, management, and planning tools) to empower individuals and groups to activate and manage civic spaces.
 - Expand the **capacity for autonomous decision-making, development, and design**, enhancing civic agency.
 4. **Establish and train the role of the community manager**
 - Recognise and strengthen the **community manager** as a bridge figure between communities and institutions.
 - Enhance training on **intercultural skills and institutional language**, shaping a **hybrid role**, both **horizontal and vertical**, capable of activating grassroots processes and influencing policy.
 5. **Promote art and culture as relational infrastructures**
 - Use artistic and cultural practices to **foster inclusive encounters and build non-judgmental, open environments**.
 - Integrate art and culture into participatory frameworks as tools for **social mediation and innovation**.
 6. **Acknowledge the digital sphere as an emerging civic space**
 - Recognise and cultivate the **potential of digital environments** to enable self-organisation and civic participation.
 - Critically reflect on the **relationship between digital and physical spaces**, promoting mindful and empowering use of technology.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Formalize the concept of general interest as a normative bridge in Europe**
 - Encourage a shared definition at EU level linking civic participation, commons, and public policy, making **bottom-up care practices legally visible and legitimate**.
2. **Design civic spaces to be beautiful, accessible, and non-exclusive**
 - Follow existing models (e.g. *Case del Quartiere* manifesto) to ensure **plural use, spatial recurrence, and aesthetic quality** of civic environments.
3. **Protect civic spaces as democratic infrastructures**

- Counteract security-focused narratives by framing civic spaces as **bastions of democracy, cohesion, and community**, worthy of **defense and long-term investment**.
- 4. Develop collaborative territorial ecosystems**
- Connect spaces, people, and local institutions to build a **shared governance model** based on cooperation and social innovation
 - Invest on **capacity building strategies for a new generation of civic spaces promoters** (social community organisations) and on networking among them (communities of practices and of affinities)
- 5. Strengthen civic and digital literacy**
- Offer educational paths for citizens, community managers, and public actors to foster **informed, inclusive, and digitally aware civic engagement**.

6. Possible future activities to protect, promote, support civic space in the territory

<p>Plan of actions, responsibilities, deadlines</p>	<p>Strategic Summary: A Generative Model</p> <p>An innovative model of public policy, born from the bottom up, placing the individual at the centre as a process enabler, and recognising civic spaces as laboratories of democracy, social economy, and cultural and social innovation.</p> <p>Key Actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Formalize the political and generative role of civic spaces ● Promote the social economy as a pillar of public action ● Enable self-organisation and co-decision mechanisms ● Invest in hybrid and relational professional roles
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7. Conclusion: Final remarks and next steps

Civic spaces in Turin are living infrastructures of democracy, fostering participation, community care, and local decision-making. They function as arenas of activism, hubs for civic economies, and platforms for cultural and social expression.

Their success depends not only on funding or buildings, but on relationships, trust, and shared purpose. Supporting them means investing in the everyday practice of participation, from activists to families, from informal groups to institutional actors. No one-size-fits-all solution exists, civic spaces vary widely in form, function, and governance. Policymaking must accommodate this diversity while promoting shared democratic values and social equity.

Despite their growing importance as democratic infrastructures, civic spaces in Turin face a range of structural and operational challenges that hinder their inclusiveness, sustainability, and long-term impact.

1.5 B. RIGHT SPACES in Rome

Overview	
<i>A concise overview presenting: key points discussed, objections and critical issues, proposed actions</i>	
<p>The Rome Policy Lab built a reflection process involving the main actors of the city's Civic Spaces to foster debate on participatory policies. At the centre of the reflection was the search for factors hindering the stabilisation of participatory policies promoted by the current Administration through numerous programmatic documents and programmes. The protagonists of civil society and Public Administration were involved, and with each of them, enabling factors, obstacles, and threats to civic spaces were analyzed, using part of the taxonomy and checklist provided by the project guidelines." Key points discussed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The nature of the city's Civic Spaces. • The fragmentation of policies and funding that support them. • The "organ pipe" model of the PA that does not provide for cross-cutting political and administrative commitment. • The long-term stabilisation of administrative practices difficult to change. • The psycho-social factors underlying the attitudes and behaviours of civil society and public administration actors. <p>The Policy Lab consisted of four different actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A focus group with the political secretariat of the Councillor of the Metropolitan City of Rome Capital for the analysis of the political will to address changes. • A focus group with Civic Hubs and Neighbourhood Labs to analyze their obstacles and critical issues. • A Future Lab with many Civic Spaces in the city to capture visions and expectations for the future. • A workshop with part of the city administration to analyze obstacles, critical issues, and opportunities for change. 	
1. Introduction	
Brief context of the sessions	<p>References to participating stakeholders (organisations, institutions, individuals), how they were contacted and involved, session program, main topics covered, etc.", Involved:</p> <p>Civil society organisations were involved in an online Focus Group and a Future Lab.</p> <p>Civil society organisations were involved in two events:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The focus group with Civic Hubs and Neighbourhood Labs aimed to: discuss and deepen the situation of Civic Spaces in Rome based on the Checklist. 2. "The Future Lab aimed to inspire and stimulate an idea of the future of Civic Spaces, to foster and strengthen the awareness of people, institutions, and civil society organisations regarding their potential." <p>The Public Administration was involved in two events:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The focus group with the secretariat of the Councillor of the Municipality and Metropolitan City of Rome Capital with a delegation for participation;

	<p>2. Workshop '<i>Civic Spaces in Rome. What institutional stance to defend rights, participation, and freedoms?</i>' aimed at reflecting on the possibilities and tools to provide a unified framework for the participatory practices and policies of Roma Capitale.</p> <p>The two focus groups and the workshop were organized by closed invitation, with a selected group of invitees involved individually through phone contacts and a subsequent invitation email. For the organisation of the Future Lab, an open invitation, an electronic poster was created and published on the portal of the Lazio Volunteering Service Centre, reduced in format for circulation on WhatsApp, and a registration form was proposed.</p>
<p>Overview of how data was collected</p>	<p>The preparation of the Policy Lab was conducted by deepening relations with the actors already involved in the Survey. To share ongoing analyses with interlocutors, a Drive folder was created with project Deliverables and Reports. In addition to phone contacts and personalized email invitations, project researchers participated in some city events bringing together representatives of Civic Spaces and followed the public activities of the Civic Hubs. Materials, research, and publications related to the proposed themes were also collected. For the involvement of the administration, with the presence of politicians and the general secretariat of Roma Capitale, however, it was necessary to organize the first internal Focus Group within the political secretariat of the Councillor delegated to participation of the Metropolitan City. The formalisation of this meeting allowed for the realisation of the administrators' workshop.</p>
<p>2. Main results</p>	
<p>Thematic Area 1</p>	<p>Disconnection between territorial needs and policies. Existence in the city and metropolitan area of neighbourhoods and places of extreme fragility, far from public intervention, which have developed their own languages and survival strategies and forms of illegality, often self-governed, particularly in relation to housing. In these situations, it is necessary to identify good practices, overcoming the obstacle of illegality, recognising their knowledge and innovative capacity. The issue should be read in terms of the 'demand for public services'.</p>
<p>Thematic Area 2</p>	<p>The fragmentation of policies and interventions concerning the Public Administration, starting from budget construction and thus fund management, is complementary to the fragmentation, temporariness, and often self-referentiality of interventions. A structured plan is needed that can build cross-cutting local policies that recompose social policies, housing policies, heritage, work, education and participation.</p>
<p>Thematic Area 3</p>	<p>The vibrancy of existing interventions, also in response to the impulses of the Regulations for Common Goods and Civic Hubs, must be translated into more structured forms of participation and become a generative process, as well as one of coordination and relationship with administrations.</p>

3. Challenges and Barriers: summary of the main challenges identified

A. The challenge of the collaborative approach with two main factors:

1. The complexity of the city of Rome, articulated in a central administration and fifteen partially autonomous Municipalities and dotted with numerous civic practices that arise spontaneously and, at times, in conflict with the public actor, hinder every solution and make times very long.
2. The recent history of the Capitoline administration, marked by a critical event involving the relationship between civil society entities and Public Administration, negatively affects the path towards shared administration and Public/Private Partnership. The Departments and related Departments do not collaborate with each other, and civil society still experiences a competitive stance given by the still almost exclusively contractual relationship with the Public Administration.

B. The challenge of managing specialized, technical, and practical knowledge is articulated in three interconnected challenges:

1. The challenge of illegality: many civic realities born with a confrontational approach to the Public Administration retain ample grey areas, e.g., occupations that have for years compensated for the lack of a housing policy. We see a series of urban policies increasingly characterized by a rhetoric aimed at legality and the consequent delegitimation of all those realities that are in this grey space.
2. The challenge of access to participatory practices for excluded communities and vulnerable individuals: currently, Civic Spaces are requesting to be recognised as intermediate bodies for their ability to involve citizens and take charge of common instances. The issue is not resolved either from a regulatory and normative point of view, or from the point of view of the participatory practices that the Civic Spaces themselves manage to implement.
3. The challenge of conflict between knowledge and practices: the involvement of universities in the mediation between Public Administration and citizenship exposes to the risk of "sterilizing" participation if the Academy, instead of serving the valorisation of all knowledge, positions itself as the sole repository of Knowledge with a capital K. The amount of funding granted with the PNRR has brought this subject into the field even beyond collaborations already underway for some time that have been able to work on the contamination of knowledge. At times, the presence of strong knowledge risks delegitimizing local politics without replacing it in the effective taking charge of the population's instances.

C. The challenge of cross-cultural integration: participatory policies must pay particular attention to the migratory universe gravitating in the city. Multiple forms of service, dedicated associations, and ethnic associations are involved.

4. Opportunities and Strengths: summary of positive aspects or enabling factors observed

The city of Rome seems to have received, with the current administration, a new impetus to make the principle of civic participation, from below, concrete and actionable, forming the basis of many acts and programmatic documents, with the publication of important Regulations that make the structural elements of participatory policies more stable: Regulation of Common Goods and Regulation of Civic Hubs. Resolutions and implementing regulations on Shared Administration. There are also programs such as Roma Scuola Aperta that stimulate the creation of educating communities and link to the Open and Participatory Schools movement active for over 20 years.

PNRR funding offers an unusual amount of resources for urban regeneration. The Metropolitan City Strategic Plan contains important indications regarding the participatory direction of policies.

5. Proposals and Recommendations: Proposed strategies and actions, divided by priority or timing (short term, medium term, long term...)

Short term:

Activation of a permanent coordination table of Civic Spaces with the local Administration to envision public policies, where it is possible to submit and discuss proposals in an open debate, participate in real decision-making processes, and collaborate in the implementation of decisions taken;

The opening of the Urban Centre with real mediation and participation functions for the Civic Hubs;

The work of the Department of Social Policies, with the Municipalities, on the toolbox for shared administration.

Medium term:

For the PA: change in administrative practices from service outsourcing to collaboration with civil society;

For civil society: acquisition of collaborative practices, development and increase of trust among civic realities. Acquisition of political subjectivity of social work;

PA investment in terms of funding, spaces, and administrative structure for the recognition of the functions of Civic Spaces and civil society investment in cultural and participatory practices aimed at citizenship and collaboration between entities.

Long term:

Organisational change of Roma Capitale: reform of the budget structure to allow for cross-cutting policies; political attention to the collaborative approach and abandonment of the Contracts Code (valid for profit activities) for the management of social services and interventions.

Cultural change of civil society and PA towards collaborative and participatory practices and the ability to positively manage conflicts.

6. Possible future activities for the protection, promotion, and support of civic space in the territory

<p>Action responsibilities, deadlines</p> <p>plan,</p>	<p>As foreseen by the Transformative Commitment of Roma Capitale for the 15-minute city, the following have been approved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulation for the shared administration of tangible and intangible common goods (DAC n.103/2023); • Register of Active Citizenship and Civic Networks; • New regulation for Participatory Budget; • Regulation of Integrated Civic Hubs for social mutualism; • Relaunch of the Widespread School for Participation and Digital Citizenship; • Organisation of events in the suburbs aimed at enhancing local participatory resources. <p>The intention to organize "Training courses for citizens and public employees" was not met.</p>
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	<p>Civic Hubs are funded through public calls for small activity programs. On the Roma Capitale portal, there is a section dedicated to participation.</p> <p>The Department of Urban Planning will open the city's Urban Centre in December, a Civic Space for collaboration and meeting between all city Civic Spaces and direct citizen use and participation.</p> <p>The Department of Social Policies of Roma Capitale has published a 'Toolbox' to share with the Municipalities the tools of shared administration, in particular co-programming and co-design that transform the relationship between civil society and Public Administration.</p> <p>The Metropolitan City will renew its Metropolitan Strategic Plan next autumn, which will include recommendations for local participatory approaches. The work on innovation initiated with the participation tables dedicated to migrants continues. A presented project is awaiting approval that will lead to the Esquilino Civic Hub being recognised at a ministerial level to build a network with other civic hubs to identify social watchdogs against racial discrimination.</p> <p>Civic Hubs continue to increase their number in neighbourhoods and Municipalities, have a Register, and work on their development and the development of city coordination to form a new type of intermediate body. Network connections are active through coordination and spontaneously activated mutual aid contacts.</p>
<p>7. Conclusion: final observations and next steps</p>	
<p>The Policy Lab was created to form the basis of long-term work that can offer the administration and Civic Spaces a common ground for growth. Through CSV Lazio and with the collaboration of the Parsec Association, it will be possible to support the construction of the permanent table and follow the work of the networks in their evolution towards acquiring the role of new intermediate bodies.</p>	

2. Civic Spaces in Europe. Comparative Analysis and Strategic Recommendations

2.1 The Strategic Value of Comparative Analysis for European Policies

In an era marked by increasing polarisation, distrust towards institutions, and the weakening of the social fabric, civic participation represents a vital necessity for the health of modern democracies. A comparative analysis of experiences conducted in Rome, Turin, Warsaw, Barcelona, and Torres Vedras, funded by the CERV program, is of crucial importance. This is not merely a collection of best practices, but a strategic investigation to understand how to strengthen the foundations of European democracy from the bottom up. This approach allows for:

- Promoting structured mutual learning: Going beyond simple experience sharing to systematically understand the potential, critical issues, and evolutions of approaches to civic spaces. Creating a "community of practice" at the European level means developing common methodologies, shared indicators, and permanent exchange platforms that accelerate the learning curve of administrators, activists, and operators across the continent.
- Identifying recurring models and principles: Identifying, from diverse local realities, those enabling factors and obstacles that appear regularly. This process allows for moving from episodic interventions to a solid framework, useful for formulating policy recommendations that, while adaptable, have broader validity and applicability.
- Developing "context-sensitive" policies: Understanding the unique territorial, cultural, and administrative dynamics of each city is essential to avoid the mistake of imposing "one-size-fits-all" solutions. Comparative analysis allows for the creation of multi-level strategies that promote shared values (democracy, inclusion, collaboration), in line with European frameworks like the Pact of Amsterdam, but which translate into concrete actions that respect local specificities.
- Building integrated and preventive strategies: Abandoning the logic of emergency to adopt a preventive and generative approach. Investing in civic spaces means investing in the social and relational infrastructure of our cities. This report demonstrates how moving from fragmented solutions to comprehensive strategies can ensure a more rooted and transformative democracy, capable of facing the complex challenges of the future.

2.2 Common Enabling Factors for Civic Participation

From the cross-cutting analysis of the five cities, key elements emerge that, if present and supported, significantly foster citizen engagement. These form the foundation upon which effective public policies can be built.

- Accessible, "porous," and flexible physical spaces: The availability of physical locations is the sine qua non condition. But it's not enough. These spaces must be open, public, and perceived as such. Informality and multifunctionality are crucial: a former factory in Turin that becomes a cultural centre, a library in Warsaw that opens its rooms to neighbourhood associations, an abandoned courtyard that transforms into a community garden. "Porosity" is the ability of these places to be freely traversed, without formal (registrations, payments) or psychological barriers, thus becoming natural catalysts for encounter, socialisation, and serendipity.
- Stable, diversified, and patient economic support: Economic stability is the most critical factor. Clear, multi-year, and trust-based funding programs are essential. Dependence on annual funds forces organisations into an exhausting cycle of reporting and fundraising, diverting energy from their core mission. Sustainability is achieved through hybrid models

that combine stable public funds with revenue from economic activities (e.g., bars, courses), philanthropy, and crowdfunding. This not only ensures survival but also strengthens autonomy and innovation capacity.

- Collaborative governance and genuine co-design: Collaboration is not consultation. It is a structured process of power sharing. The implementation of stable networks (like the network of neighbourhood houses in Turin or the MALS in Warsaw) and the use of legal instruments like "Patti di collaborazione" (Collaboration Pacts) in Italy allow for formalizing this cooperation. The co-creation of programs with residents, where citizens are not just users but designers, strengthens the sense of ownership and collective responsibility, transforming spaces into true common goods.
- The key role of professional facilitators: Participation is not spontaneous; it must be cultivated. The presence of professional figures such as cultural mediators, community managers, and process facilitators is indispensable. These professionals possess specific skills: conflict mediation, intercultural communication, participatory design, fundraising. They are not mere volunteers, but key figures who need formal recognition, continuous training, and fair remuneration. They are the "weavers" who connect needs and re-sources, people and institutions.
- Territorial rootedness and deep contextual knowledge: An effective civic space is one that "speaks the language" of its neighbourhood. This means knowing the local history, the shopkeepers, the latent tensions, the hidden resources. Territorial rootedness is what allows for building trust over time, intercepting unexpressed needs, and becoming a credible point of reference for the community, especially for the most vulnerable groups.
- Smart integration between physical and digital: Digital platforms do not replace the public square, but they can expand it. Tools like Decidim in Barcelona or simple WhatsApp groups can enhance organisation, communication, and deliberative dynamics, also reaching those who, for various reasons, cannot participate physically. However, this integration must be managed with awareness, addressing the digital divide and creating clear protocols to ensure constructive and safe debate, preventing the risks of exclusion and online toxicity.
- Structural political and institutional recognition: Recognition cannot be limited to an inauguration or a mention in a speech. It must be structural. This means integrating civic spaces into urban strategies (master plans, social services plans), including them stably in budgets, and formally recognising them as political actors and partners in the co-production of public policies. This step gives them the legitimacy and stability necessary to operate in the long term.
- Culture and art as universal languages of dialogue: Artistic and cultural activities are confirmed as powerful tools for inclusion. A theatrical project involving historical residents and newcomers, a mural workshop that redevelops a grey wall, a neighbourhood music festival: these initiatives create contexts of non-judgmental dialogue, where differences become a richness and not a barrier. Art allows for exploring complex identities and building bridges between different communities in a creative and non-conflictual way.

2.3 Common Obstacles and Critical Issues

Despite their enormous potential, civic spaces face numerous systemic problems that undermine their effectiveness and survival. Recognising them is the first step to overcoming them.

- Economic fragility and the "cycle of precariousness": Dependence on annual or short-term project-based grants creates a vicious circle. Uncertainty prevents hiring qualified permanent staff, leading to high turnover and loss of historical memory. The constant "grant chasing" consumes time and energy that should be dedicated to activities, generating a sense of perpetual precariousness that wears down even the most motivated individuals.
- Suffocating bureaucracy and clash of cultures: The complexity, slowness, and rigidity of administrative procedures represent a huge obstacle. There is a real "clash of cultures" between the agile, flexible, and trust-based logic of community initiatives and the slow, hierarchical, and formal control-based logic of public administrations. Obtaining permits for a simple neighbourhood festival can require months of paperwork, discouraging participation.
- Ineffective communication and invisibility: Many civic spaces remain "invisible" to a large part of the citizenry. Institutional communication often uses bureaucratic and self-referential language, conveyed through traditional channels that do not reach younger or marginalized audiences. There is a lack of ability to communicate the value generated in an engaging and accessible way, using the languages and platforms (from social media to word-of-mouth) of the communities they want to reach.
- Barriers to access and superficial inclusivity: Inclusivity is often declared but rarely fully practiced. Barriers are not only physical (absence of ramps, inaccessible bathrooms) but also cultural (activities that do not reflect the diversity of the neighbourhood), linguistic (materials only in the majority language), and social. The dominance of pre-existing groups can create a closed atmosphere, where newcomers feel uncomfortable or unwelcome, transforming the space into an exclusive context rather than a common good.
- Lack of recognition and spiral of distrust: Mutual distrust between citizens and administrations generates a negative spiral. Institutions, not trusting, impose excessive controls and micro-management actions. Communities, feeling controlled and undervalued, disengage or adopt an antagonistic attitude. This lack of trust, combined with the lack of formal recognition of professional roles, hinders any form of authentic and equal collaboration.
- Burn-out and the human cost of participation: Behind every civic space there are people. Volunteers and coordinators face enormous workloads, high responsibilities, emotional stress, and often inadequate or absent remuneration. Burnout is a real epidemic in this sector, with a very high human cost: passionate and competent people leaving, loss of relationships and skills, and a deterioration in the quality of initiatives.
- The multiple faces of digital civic space:
 - First and second-level digital divide: Exclusion concerns not only those who do not have access to a device or connection (first level), but also those who, despite having them, do not possess the skills, motivation, or trust to use them critically and consciously (second level). This gap penalizes the elderly, low-income individuals, and migrants.
 - Pollution of debate: disinformation and hate speech: The online environment, if not governed, becomes fertile ground for the spread of fake news, extreme polarisation, and incitement to hatred. These phenomena can poison local debate, undermine social cohesion, and sabotage participatory processes.
 - The dilemma of privacy and the "chilling effect": The massive collection of data and the fear of surveillance can induce people to self-censorship ("chilling effect"), limiting freedom of expression and the willingness to participate in discussions on sensitive topics, for fear of being judged or penalized.

2.4 *Insights into the Policy Labs*

Policy Labs were important for presenting and discussing ongoing local activities, identifying opportunities, critical issues, good practices, and lessons learned. In particular, the third and fourth Policy Labs offered the involved territories the opportunity to share progress in developing civic space initiatives, exchange learnings, and collectively reflect on emerging challenges and future steps. The format was open and interactive, allowing each local group to contribute with reflections based on activities undertaken or planned. Various concerns but also interesting innovative approaches emerged as recurring themes among the territories, which can translate in-to a rich basis for the development of dedicated policies.

- Disconnection between civic initiatives and institutional frameworks/political influence: This was a central theme for Turin, which identified a gap between grassroots engagement and the ability to influence public policies. Rome also highlighted this disconnection and the difficulty of involving political actors resistant to change. Warsaw emphasised the lack of trust between institutions and administrative bodies towards civic activities and the imposed restrictions. However, Rome showed success in involving high-level stakeholders in the fourth partner lab, improving the synthesis between civic spaces and institutional actors.
- Access to public space and restrictive regulations: Barcelona highlighted the difficulty of organizing activities outside their physical premises due to restrictive regulations and authorisation processes. This connects to the need to recognise the social value of spaces compared to their commercial value.
- Legal and political recognition of civic spaces: A key request that emerged in Barcelona is the need for new legal and political recognition of civic spaces, not as private actors or service providers, but as common goods, with their own governance models and value production. This implies the need to explore legal and administrative frameworks that support civic spaces, as also foreseen by Warsaw's plan. Discussions in Barcelona also examined how regulations facilitate or hinder the creation of civic networks.
- Sustainability of activism and civic spaces: In Turin, the issue of the fine line between volunteering and employment emerged, raising issues of labour rights, exploitation, and the sustainability of activism. Warsaw reported burnout among civic space workers, due to poor funding, lack of preferential rents, and limited human resources. Turin also addressed the tensions between activist identity, sustainability, and risks of institutional over-identification.
- Importance of networks and support: Turin highlighted the importance of networks in promoting resilience and influence, while Warsaw expressed a strong desire for networking not only for strategic coordination but also for emotional and institutional support.
- Youth involvement: Turin had a specific focus on young people, who emphasised informality, gratuity, and a sense of belonging. Torres Vedras also planned a discussion group focused on youth involvement, building on the existing municipal youth council.
- Role of social economy organisations: Their role in the functioning and sustainability of civic spaces was recognised as relevant, and their identification and strengthening of their involvement were deemed crucial.
- Common tools and methodologies: The use of the B.RIGHT SPACES checklist and taxonomy was recommended to help identify key dimensions to explore with participants, experts, and stakeholders. Local methodologies were encouraged and analyzed for possible integration into the project's final guidelines.

2.5 *The Local Contexts: A Mosaic of Peculiarities and Opportunities*

Each city presents a unique picture, the study of which is essential to understanding the complexity of the phenomenon and avoiding generalisations.

- Rome: The paradox of complexity. The Italian capital is an emblematic case of paradox. From one side, it possesses highly advanced regulatory instruments (common goods regulation, civic poles); from the other side, its enormous scale and fragmented "organ-pipe" administrative structure make the implementation of such instruments extremely difficult. Many of the most innovative practices arise in "grey areas" (informal or occupied), acting as a kind of "de facto subsidiarity" that makes up for public shortcomings and highlights the constant tension between the rhetoric of legality and unmet social needs.
- Turin: Maturity and its risks. The Piemonte region capital boasts one of the most consolidated participatory governance experiences in Europe, embodied by the network of Neighbourhood Houses, true "urban democratic infrastructures." The challenge here is that of maturity: the risk of progressive bureaucratisation, excessive dependence on public funds, and a "co-optation" that transforms these grassroots spaces into mere service providers on behalf of the municipality, losing their transformative and critical charge.
- Warsaw: Democratic resilience at the urban level. The Polish model, based on Local Activity Centres, is strongly supported by the municipality with multi-year funding and access to premises. In a national context marked by strong political tensions, municipal support for civic spaces takes on added value, configuring itself as a strategy of democratic resilience at the local level. The main challenges, however, remain the risk of burnout for operators, the pressure of gentrification, and vulnerability to possible changes in political direction.
- Barcelona (Catalonia): The struggle for the right to the city. Here, the debate is strongly focused on the role of community culture as a barrier to hate speech and on the fight against the privatisation of public space. The "showcase city" model, oriented towards mass tourism, generates conflicts and inequalities. Civic spaces and community management of assets emerge as a form of resistance and claim to the "right to the city" by residents, but they clash with legal uncertainty that limits their development.
- Torres Vedras: The challenge of autonomy. In this Portuguese city, the approach is centred on cultural policies as a matrix for civic development. The main criticality, however, is a perceived excessive centralisation and paternalism on the part of the municipality. By acting as the main cultural programmer, the public body creates, even unintentionally, strong dependence and competition that limit the autonomy and vitality of the independent associative fabric.

The challenge is to move from a delivery model to an enablement model.

2.6 *Strategic Recommendations for Public Policies*

To overcome the challenges and enhance the potential of civic spaces, a strategic, coherent, and multi-level approach is recommended, acting simultaneously at European, national, and local levels.

A) At European and national level:

1. Reform and innovate regulatory frameworks: It is necessary to go beyond current directives. Develop an "EU Charter for the Valorisation of Civic Spaces" that establishes clear principles such as the right to community management, subsidiarity, and access to non-competitive funds.

At the national level, it is crucial to promote laws that recognise collaboration between the public and organized local citizenry as an equal relationship, overcoming the rigidities and inadequacy of public procurement regulations for this type of initiative.

2. Promote digital sovereignty and skills: The EU and member states should invest massively in the development of public and open-source digital infrastructures for participation, as alternatives to commercial platforms. In parallel, it is essential to finance large-scale programs of digital civic education and media literacy to provide citizens with the tools to participate critically, safely, and constructively.
3. Institutionalize stable, flexible, and continuous funding: Encourage member states to implement multi-year funding cycles as a standard for recognised civic spaces. It is necessary to explore innovative mechanisms such as national endowment funds for civic action or the allocation of a fixed share of European structural funds to local democracy and participation initiatives.

B) At local and regional level:

1. Establish permanent "governance ecosystems": Not just consultation tables, but real co-decision spaces. These permanent coordination tables must have clear mandates, power to direct budgets, and plural representation of administrators, technicians, civic actors, and citizens. They must become the "place" where trust is built and policies are co-designed.
2. Formalize and support participation professions: Recognising and financially supporting key roles such as community managers and facilitators is an investment, not a cost. This means creating professional registers, including these figures in public contracts, and investing in university courses and continuous training to ensure a high level of competence in fields such as social and intercultural mediation, conflict management, and participatory design.
3. Develop open, inclusive, and participatory governance models: Design spaces (physical and digital) "by design" accessible to all, eliminating all barriers. Adopt management models that actively involve citizens, for example through participatory budgets for the management of the space itself, open assemblies, and user committees with decision-making power.
4. Adopt new narratives and enhance community communication: Develop awareness campaigns and clear communication models, but above all invest in community media. Train local "storytellers," use narrative evaluation to communicate impact, and use the channels and languages that communities already use to create an authentic and bi-directional communication flow.
5. Integrate civic infrastructure into strategic urban planning: Make civic infrastructure a central element and not an "afterthought" in urban development plans. This means providing for "civic impact assessments" for new urban projects, mapping and protecting existing spaces, and ensuring that the maintenance and adequacy of structures are an investment priority.

In conclusion, the creation and support of structured civic spaces require a holistic approach and a paradigm shift. This is not a simple "social" policy, but a fundamental investment in the resilience, innovation, and quality of European democracy itself. It is not enough to provide infrastructure; it is crucial to invest in the "invisible" infrastructure of relationships, trust, skills, and a profound cultural change in both public administration and civil society. Collective commitment in this direction can lead to building the foundations for more pluralistic and equitable democracies.

2.7 Digital Civic Spaces: Characteristics, Critical Issues, and Development Paths

The advent of the digital age has triggered a profound redefinition of how citizens interact, express opinions, and mobilize for collective causes. This process has fostered the emergence and consolidation of "digital civic spaces," conceived as virtual arenas that complement and, in some contexts, tend to replace traditional physical spaces for aggregation and debate. Understanding these spaces is crucial for the formulation of effective public policies by the European Union and local authorities, aimed at promoting inclusive development consistent with democratic values. This chapter offers a multidimensional analysis of digital civic spaces, examining their characteristics, critical issues, and outlining development paths and public policies.

Characteristics and specificities of Digital Civic Spaces

The concept of civic space, in its most general sense, refers to an environment, physical or metaphorical, that enables individuals and groups to participate meaningfully in the political, economic, social, and cultural life of their respective societies, exercising fundamental rights such as freedom of association, peaceful assembly, and expression. Digital civic space represents its natural extension in the online environment, configuring itself as a virtual sphere in which these rights and freedoms find expression through digital technologies and platforms. A distinctive element is its ability to connect informal and formal networks of civic participation.

Among the main characteristics and specificities are:

- Hybrid nature (physical and digital): The evolution towards digital civic spaces is inextricably linked to the Industrial Revolution 4.0 and the internet, with a significant acceleration driven by the COVID-19 pandemic. This shift has introduced unprecedented dynamics and potentials, such as greater potential accessibility, broader inclusion, and rapid mobilisation. However, digital does not replace physical but complements it, with hybrid models (online/offline) representing the most promising solution for inclusive and deep engagement.
- Distinction from commercial "social web": To be authentic, digital civic spaces require specific "design criteria," oriented towards the public good and the promotion of authentic and meaningful participation, rather than profit logic or superficial engagement. Existing commercial platforms are not optimized for constructive deliberation or broad inclusion. This implies an intentional and, potentially, non-commercial or heavily regulated approach.

- Diversified functions and objectives: Digital civic spaces are designed to:
 - Facilitate communication and collaboration by connecting people with common interests.
 - Disseminate information and promote awareness on social, political, economic, and environmental issues.
 - Mobilize support for social causes through crowdfunding, online petitions, and public opinion mobilisation.
 - Create online communities and promote inclusion, particularly for isolated individuals or groups.
 - Democratize access to information and educational resources, fostering citizen empowerment.
 - Support social innovation through idea collection, collaborative funding, and co-operation.
 - Improve governmental transparency and accountability with open data and public forums.
 - Enable participation in legislative and policy-making processes.
 - Promote specific commitments on digital rights and the availability of disaggregated data. These functions transcend mere information transmission, focusing on tangible action and social change. The goal is to "connect networks of net-works" and facilitate co-productive relationships between citizens and institutions.
 - Specific cultural aspects: They develop around values such as transparency, collaboration, openness, inclusivity, responsibility, and equity. Norms of behaviour (netiquette) and a specific language or jargon may emerge that can strengthen group identity. They facilitate the formation of "discourse communities" and collective identities. However, phenomena such as "slacktivism" (superficial activism) and a marked participatory inequality (e.g., 90-9-1 rule) are observed, which question the democratic nature and representativeness of digital participation. Effective participation requires not only technological access but also a solid "digital culture" and key skills (digital literacy, computer literacy, media literacy, critical thinking).
 - Organisational and governance aspects: They can have governance models ranging from centralized to co-managed. "Platform governance" includes citizens and media as relevant actors. Roles such as administrators, moderators, participants/users, and facilitators are identified. Decision-making processes vary from consultative to co-decisional, with platforms like Decidim emphasizing transparency and traceability. The adoption of digital spaces implies a rethinking of in-ternal workflows and decision-making processes of institutions. "Platformisation" raises the need for "digital public infrastructure" (public or community digital infrastructures) to ensure democratic sovereignty.
 - Content and service aspects: They offer a wide range of information (news, open data, policy documents) and discussion tools (forums, chats, petitions). They provide resources for learning and civic action (guides, training) and, in some cases, real transactional services (e.g., reports, payments, online participatory budgeting). The "content-as-a-service" (CAAS) model aims to maximize communication reach by making content accessible on multiple channels.
 - Operational aspects: accessibility and moderation - interactions can be synchro-nous or asynchronous. Levels of participation vary from information, consultation, collaboration/dialogue to co-design/co-decision. Content moderation is crucial for a safe environment but complex due to volume, cultural/linguistic nuances, risks of bias

(human and AI), and lack of transparency. Accessibility and usability are fundamental for inclusion, with the adoption of standards such as WCAG and EN 301 549.

Emerging Critical Issues in the Development and Management of Digital Civic Spaces

Despite their potential, digital civic spaces face numerous problems that can limit their effectiveness and democratic impact:

- **Digital divide and risks of exclusion:** The digital divide persists and manifests not only as a lack of material access (infrastructure, costs) but also as a gap in digital skills (digital literacy), motivation, and connection quality. It affects vulnerable categories such as the elderly, immigrants, people with disabilities, low-income individuals, and residents in rural areas. This divide is closely linked to a knowledge gap, limiting access to information and opportunities, and compromising "digital citizenship" for large segments of the population.
- **Disinformation, manipulation, and polarisation:** The digital environment is fertile ground for the proliferation of "fake news" and disinformation campaigns on crucial issues. Social media are used to distort electoral processes, pollute public debate, and incite violence/hatred. Algorithmic dynamics can foster polarisation, the creation of "echo chambers," and the amplification of extreme views. This problem is systemic and requires equally systemic responses.
- **Data security, privacy, and surveillance:** Digitisation involves massive collection of personal data, raising concerns about their security, privacy, and risks of surveillance by state or private actors. Unauthorized disclosure can expose individuals and groups to retaliation, generating a "chilling effect" that limits freedom of expression. The application of GDPR is fundamental, but its compliance can be complex for smaller organisations. The need for "digital sovereignty" emerges to protect fundamental rights. Managing digital identity (balancing authentication and anonymity) is a crucial challenge.
- **Challenges in content moderation:** Moderation is necessary but complex. Critical issues include the difficult balance between content removal and protection of freedom of expression, the enormous volume of content to manage, the difficulty of understanding context and linguistic nuances, the risks of bias (human and algorithmic), the lack of transparency and accountability in moderation processes, the impact on the mental health of human moderators, and arbitrary censorship or blocking practices. Relying on AI for moderation can lead to an "algorithmic monoculture" with cultural biases.
- **Economic sustainability and financial precariousness:** Many platforms, especially open-source or non-profit ones, depend on project funding, often short-term, discontinuous, and competitive. This "grant dependency" limits long-term planning, investments, and hiring of qualified personnel. Maintenance, security, and update costs are often underestimated.
- **Non-participatory governance, lack of accountability, and transparency:** Many platforms lack mechanisms that actively involve users and communities in key decisions. Opacity in decisions (e.g., moderation, algorithms, data usage) fuels suspicion and undermines trust. The lack of clear oversight and appeal mechanisms makes platform accountability difficult.

2.8 *Development Paths and Public Policies to Implement*

To overcome critical issues and strengthen the potential of digital civic spaces, targeted strategies and public policies are needed:

- Promote a "civic DNA" for platforms: The European Union and local authorities should promote, create, or regulate platforms endowed with an authentic "civic DNA," oriented towards the public good and authentic participation, not just profit. It is crucial to support the adoption of open-source software and non-profit organizational models.
- Ensure stable and diversified financial sustainability: It is essential to ensure multi-year and diversified funding (public, private, philanthropic) to allow for long-term planning. Investments in digital civic spaces should be considered strategic investments in essential democratic infrastructures. The creation of dedicated and specific funds for civic tech is suggested.
- Legal recognition and administrative reform: Public policies should modify regulatory frameworks to formally recognise community management and develop tools that go beyond contractual logic. A reform of administrative culture is needed to effectively welcome and integrate civic contributions into formal decision-making processes.
- Adopt a hybrid approach (online/offline): Hybrid models, which strategically combine online and offline engagement, emerge as the most promising solution for more inclusive and deep involvement. Digital platforms can serve as information and organisational hubs for physical activities, while physical spaces (libraries, community centres) can be catalysts for digital participation, offering access and training. Effectiveness depends on careful and holistic design that synergistically integrates both dimensions.
- Address the digital divide holistically: Policies must go beyond merely providing infrastructure, including massive investments in digital literacy, continuous training programmes, personalized support for vulnerable groups, and active policies to reduce access costs. It cannot be assumed that digitalisation is a universal "equalizer."
- Combat disinformation and hate speech: More stringent and responsible regulations for platforms are needed (such as the Digital Services Act and the AI Act at the European level), widespread programs for educating citizens in critical thinking and conscious media use, and robust support for quality and independent journalism. Platforms should be designed to foster constructive dialogue and mutual understanding.
- Strengthen data security and privacy: Full and correct application of GDPR with adequate technical and organisational measures is essential. The design of digital identity management systems must be secure, privacy-respecting, and flexible, balancing authentication needs and the right to anonymity. Investing in "digital sovereignty" is crucial.
- Improve the quality and transparency of moderation: It is necessary to explore and develop more participatory, transparent, and contextually sensitive moderation models. This includes greater community involvement (distributed moderation), the establishment of clear and accessible appeal mechanisms, and a more cautious and supervised use of artificial intelligence as a support tool for human moderators.
- Promote participatory governance, accountability, and transparency of platforms: Policies must encourage the creation of governance mechanisms that actively involve users and communities in key decisions related to the functioning and development of platforms. It is fundamental to ensure transparency on moderation processes, algorithmic changes, and the use of collected data, and to establish clear accountability mechanisms.

- Develop skills and capacity building: Invest in training and mentoring programs for coordinators, volunteers, and administrative staff, covering both technical skills and digital "soft skills."
- Create a networked ecosystem of civic spaces: Instead of a single monolithic space, the strategy should aim to support "networks of spaces" that are interconnected, including both local or thematic digital platforms and physical civic centres distributed throughout the territory. This approach allows for the horizontal dissemination of good practices and a deepening of civic engagement at the local level.

The future of digital civic spaces lies in the construction of resilient, hybrid, and collaborative ecosystems, where public institutions, civil society, and citizens work together with trust and shared responsibility. This requires a holistic and integrated approach that goes beyond mere technology to address the profound cultural, organisational, and political implications. Only then can digital civic spaces serve as engines of social and democratic transformation in the 21st century.